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FOREWORD

Our Journal's title recalls, a little nostalgically, *Teoria e Critica / Theory and Criticism*,¹ a periodical co-founded by Luciano Rossi in 1972. It aims to explore, in a non-dogmatic way, different gnoseological and expressive statutes of various features of the artistic production in terms of polysemic semantic relations.

Because of the specific competencies of the editorial staff, philological and hermeneutical methods are privileged without neglecting, occasionally, some new trends in criticism.

The Editors

¹ Quadrimestrale di teoria e critica della letteratura diretto da Angela Giannitrapani, Borivoje Markovic, Luciano Rossi, Roma, 1972.

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THOMAS BECKET'S LETTERS
FROM HIS EXILE AND THEIR
FRENCH TEXT

ABSTRACT

Garnier de Pont-Sainte-Maxence's *Vie de Saint Thomas* (1171–1174) preserves, in French alexandrines, three letters by Thomas Becket, sent from his exile in the year 1166. The editor of the *Vie*, E. Walberg (1922) took them to be translations of the official Latin letters. After a comparison of these French texts with the official Latin letters edited by Anne Duggan (2000) in the *Correspondence of Thomas Becket, Archbishop of Canterbury, 1162–1170*, the author of this article thinks that the letters versified by Garnier are not translations, but go back to (now lost) French letters written as parallel texts to the official Latin letters. This opinion is supported, e.g., by the French and Latin letters' diverging use of their common material; while following the same guideline, they differ in many details. Consequently, the French letters should not be neglected in Thomas Becket research: surviving outside the Latin manuscript tradition, they may add a new voice into the discussion, and even change some results.

KEY WORDS : *Thomas Becket's French and Latin letters, Garnier de Pont-Sainte-Maxence*

INTRODUCTION

England's archbishop, Thomas Becket, was murdered in the cathedral of Canterbury on the day of the Holy Innocents 1170. Before that, he spent six years in exile in France, 1164-1170, staying in letter contact with the outside world. Among the letters sent by him, three are of particular importance for our research, all from the year 1166 : *Desiderio desideravi* and *Expectans expectavi* sent to the English king Henry II, and *Mirandum et uehementer stupendum* sent to Gilbert Foliot, bishop of London.

The original documents have not survived, but together with copies of Thomas Becket's numerous other Latin letters they have been preserved in several Becket-related letter collections. Two early collections, alpha and beta, « made from records kept by Becket's household in exile » (Duggan 2000 :lxx), have been lost, but their contents and structure can be deduced by collating their descendants, the manuscripts of the Becket group (eadem lxix) ; and alpha and beta have also influenced the manuscripts of Alan of Tewkesbury's collection (eadem lxxx). The manuscripts of the Foliot group remain outside the influence of alpha and beta : we will return to these important manuscripts (*infra*). – The letter *Desiderio* and a short version of the letter *Mirandum* are also included by Edward Grim in his *Thomas Becket Vita* (1172).¹

¹ Edited in Robertson, Mat. 2, 409-412 (Edward Grim, *Mirandum*), and 419-421 (Edward Grim, *Desiderio*).

Thomas Becket's Latin letters have been edited by J. C. Robertson in vol. 5 of *Materials for the History of Thomas Becket* (1881) and recently by Anne Duggan in *The Correspondence of Thomas Becket, Archbishop of Canterbury, 1162–1170* (2000). – With a solid introduction, and a rich apparatus for *uariae lectiones*, Duggan's text² is based on the manuscript *a* (London, BL, MS Cotton Claudius B.ii, Duggan 2000: cxi). This fine manuscript, dated to the late 1170s or early 1180s (Duggan 2000: lxxxiv), represents the Alan of Tewkesbury collection. Duggan's excellent edition is provided with an English translation that will be used in this article (the author will be giving her own only for some *uerbatim* renderings).

In addition, *La Vie de Saint Thomas Becket* (from ca. 1174) by Garnier or Guernes³ de Pont-Sainte-Maxence has preserved, in French verse, the already-mentioned three letters, *Expectans* and *Desiderio* (in that order) to Henri II, and *Mirandum* addressed to Gilbert Foliot, bishop of London, who had written to Thomas Becket

² Unlike Robertson, Duggan does not modify the manuscripts' graphies according some norm, classical or other, but follows the spelling of the manuscript "except that the hooked *e* is not reproduced and *J/j* is rendered as *I/i*" (Duggan 2000: cxi). We use Duggan's edition.

³ Walberg, and after him most resarchers use the form *Guernes*. (Janet Shirley's 1975 translation of *Garniers Becket* being an exception.) *Guernes* is short form corresponding to *Garnier* (<*warin-hari*). Both are found in the *Vie de Saint Thomas Becket*. The author uses the short form when talking about himself: *Guernes li Clers, del Punt Sainte Mesence nez/ Vus volt faire del tens del martyre acertez* (5877–5978), and *Guernes li Clers del Punt fine ici sun sermun* (6156); but he is called Garnier by other people *Se nuls me dit "Guarniers, ou vas?"* (appendix, v.14; the appendix is preserved in the manuscript P of the *Vie* and published by Walberg after the main text). Cf. Bob/ Robert, Bill/William.

on behalf of the English clergy that stood on Henry II's side in the conflict. The clergy's letter, *Que uestro pater*, is also versified by Garnier (3186–3320) ; we will discuss it only in passing.

In his still authoritative edition of Garnier's text, E. Walberg (1922 : CVII)⁴ regrets the author's zeal to translate the long letters.⁵ Ever since, the French versions of these letters found in Garnier's verse are considered to be translations from Latin, recently by Short who talks about (2013 : 185) the Latin letters as the originals. This article will examine Walberg's position.

Garnier's source for the letter texts has not been ascertained, although it is known that Garnier used for his work the Thomas Becket *Vitas* of Edward Grim (1172) and of William of Canterbury (1192–1194), the former containing the letter *Desiderio* and a short version of *Mirandum*. Duggan states correctly: «[...] But it is clear that Guernes had access also to a further source of letters: not only does he provide a translation of *Exspectans exspectau*, which occurs

⁴ We have used both editions of Emmanuel Walberg (the scholarly edition from 1922 and the popular format edition from 1936). Recently, Walberg's edition served as a basis for J.T.E. THOMAS's *La Vie de Saint Thomas de Canterbury* (2002). This edition adds several valuable corrections, a detailed commentary, and a French translation. Thomas's text in turn was used by I. Short for his English translation (2013), provided with important notes. For the *Vie*, I have consulted the translations of these predecessors: although I normally give my own translations, Short's more beautiful, but freer, translation is rather frequently used.

⁵ «Et employer plus de 700 vers à traduire, d'un bout à l'autre, quatre lettres échangées entre Becket et ses adversaires»– Garnier includes Gilbert Foliot's letter to Thomas Becket as well – «au lieu de se borner à en donner un résumé, c'est évidemment un regrettable excès de zèle».

in neither of the biographies he used, but he has fuller versions of *Que uestro pater* and *Mirandum et uehementer* than those found in Grim» (1980: 203). – For the differences between Garnier and Edward Grim regarding the texts of *Desiderio* and *Mirandum*, the reader is referred to the tables at the end of this article.

Duggan's rich apparatus of variants allows us to examine Garnier's text directly with the preserved copies of the official Latin letters.

Compared with the Latin letter *Expectans*, Garnier's version of the letter seems to have one important lacuna: the passage *non uobis hec dicimus... penitebis* has no equivalence in his text; Duggan (2000:ciii, note 267) finds the same lacuna in the manuscripts C and D, two manuscripts belonging to the Foliot group. Like Garnier, C and D use in *Expectans* the familiar second person singular (*tu*) rather than the formal plural found in the other Latin manuscripts; and *sed uereor* (Duggan 328), added in C and D, reminds one of *ço criem* (Garnier 2859; 'I am afraid (of this)' used as an adverb), an integral, not superfluous, part of the French text. In *Desiderio*, the variant *conterendos*, found in CDLV* for the accepted reading *cohercendos* (Duggan 294), is semantically closer to *detrenchier* used by Garnier (3085). As seen in the tables at the end of this article, Garnier's text shares with the manuscripts C and D some minor lacunas as well.

C and D are associated with Gilbert Foliot; they are «contemporary collections which did not draw on Archetypes alpha and beta for their Becket-related correspondence, but on materials found in Foliot's own household» (Duggan 2000:ci). C (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS e Mus. 249) was prepared in this episcopal

household in London towards the end of Gilbert Foliot's life and finished soon after his death in 1187. In this manuscript, the 'Becket section'⁶ is a «propagandist compilation containing résumés of the points at issue between King Henry and Becket and Foliot and Becket» (Duggan 2000:cii). D (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS Douce 287) was copied in England during the last quarter of the twelfth century and «written as an appendix to the earliest surviving copy of William FitzStephen's *Vita sancti Thome*» (Duggan 2000:ciii).

Although the two manuscripts C and D (C in particular) seem to have more details in common with Garnier's text than with the rest of the Latin versions of Thomas Becket's letters, their overall letter texts are still not close enough to be taken as (copies of) the texts Garnier could have been translating. Indeed, Garnier's source text is not found.

Garnier's poem was probably finished already ca. 1174, but the earliest manuscripts to preserve it to our time come only from the beginning of the 13th century. Still, given the technically demanding format of his text (alexandrines arranged in five-line stanzas), as well as the inconspicuous presentation of the letters (as parts of a hagiography), and his continental dialect (that of Northern Île-de-France, with some picardisms), his version of the French letters did most likely not invite any intentional modifications by his readers or the Anglo-Norman scribes who started copying *La Vie de Saint*

⁶ The opening folio of the 'Becket section' shows signs of wear and bears the press-mark of Westminster Abbey: the part *Causa inter Cantuariensem et episcopum Londoniensem* was composed ca. 1169 (Duggan 2000:cii, also note 262).

Thomas Becket after its completion in 1174. This makes the identification of Garnier's source texts particularly interesting.

Garnier's text is preserved in six manuscripts. After a thorough study, Walberg chose to base his text on the MS B (Wolfenbüttel Herzog August Bibl., Cod. Guelf. Aug. in-4°, 34.6; early 13th c.; incomplete, lacking the first 18 folios, verses 1-1080 and, later, two folios, verses 1321-1440) completing and correcting it with readings from the MS H (London, BL, Harley 270; early 13th c.) and, in second place from the MS P (Paris, BNF, ms. fr. 13513; first half of the 13th c.), referring more seldom to other, later, manuscripts, W (BL Add. 70513, olim Welbeck Abbey I.C.1, last quart of the 13th c.), C (BL Add. 59616, olim Cheltenham Phillips 8113, 14th c.), and D (BL, Cotton Domitian A.XI, first half of the 14th c. – all dates from DEAF Bibl.).

The author has maintained (Löfstedt 1990 :4 and 1997) that the French version of the letters was done with the help of a French translation of Gratian's *Decretum*; and that this translation seems to be the text preserved in the manuscript Bruxelles BR 9084 (from ca. 1280) and recently edited (1992–2001).

Indeed, where a Latin *Decretum* passage is used in a Latin letter of Thomas Becket (quoted from Duggan's edition), Garnier's verse may mirror the French *Decretum* translation of the passage. Here are two examples (the French *Decretum* is quoted from the Löfstedt 1992–2001 edition with line numbers):

The binomial in Decr. D 96 c 16 *ecclesias contritas atque conscissas* is repeated in the letter *Expectans: ecclesias contritas et concissas* (var. *conscissas*) (Duggan 330).

In Fr. Decr. D 96 c 16, l. 2 *les iglises qui sont decheoités* the binomial is replaced by an adjectival subordinate (whose verb is a derivative of *cheoir*); likewise in Garnier (*iglises...*)/*Celes qui sont chaüés* (from *cheoir*) (2898).

Decr. C 2 q 7 c 27 *Item legitur in Libro Regum, quod cum archa Domini reduceretur de Gabaa in Hierusalem, bubus recalcitrantibus archa inclinata est, cui dum Oza ... manum adhiberet, ut eam erigeret, a Domino percussus interiit.*

Expectans differs from the *Decretum* text by giving Oza's action before its cause: *Oza quoque..., quoniam archam Dei tetigit, et tenuit nutantem ad precipitium bobus recalcitrantibus... indignatione Domini* (var. *diuina*) *percussus iuxta archam Domini corruit mortuus* (Duggan 336). Also, the syntagm *manum adhiberet* has been replaced by *tetigit et tenuit*, and *a Domino*, by *indignatione Domini* (var. *diuina*).⁷

Fr. Decr. C 2 q 7 c 27, l. 28 *L'on lit el livre des Rois que quant l'arche Dameldieu fut ramenee de Gabaa en Jerusalem, li buef eschalcirrent* (ms. *eshaucierrent*), *c'est a dire repanerent*⁸; *si s'abessa l'arche; et por ce que Oza... i mist la main por*

⁷ Oza's action is given before its cause also in the Vulgate (2. Sam.[=2 Reg.] 6.6).

⁸ Fr. Decr. uses here the same verb as the Anglo-Norman *Quatre Livre des Reis* (*Oza estendit la main vers l'arche, si la tint pur çó que li buef eschalcirrouent é alches l'enclinerent...*, 2 Reg 6, 6 [=2 Sam. 6.6], Curtius 70). The verb is found in the general meaning 'to kick', 'to kick back', and the phrase *e. contre aguillon* (cf. Vulg.Act. 26,14) is frequent (T-L 3, 869, 31). The glose *c'est a dire repanerent* is added to the French *Decretum* either by the translator or, maybe with more likelihood, by his continental scribe. The verb *repener*, *repaner*, not listed in AND, is probably not found in Anglo-Norman (Roques 2007:228). – The *Quatre Livre des Reis* is a free Anglo-Norman translation of the two Books of Samuel and the two Books of Kings interpolated with passages from the Chronicles. It is dated to the second half of the twelfth century in AND and in DEAF Bibl.

drecier la, Damedieux le feri, si que il morut. Here, *i mist la main* renders *manum adhiberet* used in the Latin *Decretum* and Oza's action is given after its cause (instability of the load).

Garnier : *Li buef eschalcirrent, l' arche voleit chair ;/ Oza i mist la main qui la volt retenir/L'ire Deu l' abati, sil fist iluec murir* (2972–2974). Oza's action is given after its cause like in the *Decretum* (Latin and French), and not before, as it is in the Latin *Expectans*. The expression *i mist la main*, too, binds Garnier's text to the French *Decretum* and not to the Latin *Expectans*. Interestingly, Garnier's verse has in common with the French *Decretum* also the verb *eschalcirrer* : Garnier « whose French was good because he was born in France » (*Mis languages est bons, car en France fui nez Garnier* 6165) uses here a verb that needed an explaining gloss *c'est a dire repanerent* in the – continental – copy of the French *Decretum*. The syntagm *L'ire Dieu* could correspond to *indignatio(ne) Domini* or *diuina* used in the Latin letter, but while *indignatione diuina* is an adverb in *Expectans*, *L'ire Dieu* is used as the subject of the phrase like *Damedieux* in the French *Decretum*.

THOMAS BECKET'S LETTERS IN GARNIER'S VERSE, A TRANSLATION ?

Admitting, after the above examples, that Garnier's French text shows influence of the French *Decretum*, we now ask whether Walberg was right in qualifying Thomas Becket's letters in Garnier's verse as translations of the Latin letter texts.

We will examine some letter passages that are not based on any *Decretum* text. Is Garnier now translating the corresponding passage in the Latin letter ?

Even a superficial comparison of the French and Latin texts shows differences between the – shorter– French text and the Latin text.

1. *Style differences : the Latin text suffers of verbosity.*

In the Latin text there are many small superfluous additions, e.g. in *Mirandum* (where Thomas Becket reports his possessions as an archdeacon, the Latin letter adds *quantum ad ea que mundi sunt* (Duggan 430), a ‘pious’ phrase without equivalence in the French text (Garnier 3410). – Longer oratorical passages jeopardize the text’s clarity. We give one example from *Mirandum*, where the emperor Constantine — who refused to judge priests — is described in the French text :

Cil fu bons emperere : Deus li duna sa grace./ Saint’iglise l’eshauce : il veit Deus face a face./Li reis devreit ensivre e ses mors e sa trace (Garnier 3543 ; ‘That one was a good emperor : God gave him His grace. The Church extolls him : he sees God face to face. The king should follow his ways and his footsteps’),

and in the Latin letter :

O magnum imperatorem ! O discrete regnantem in terra, que aliena sunt non usurpantem, et regnum eternum in celo promerentem ! Studeat ergo dominus noster rex tantum, tam discretum, tam felicem, imitari principem cuius et memoria laudabilis frequentatur in terris, et uita perpetua et gloriosa habetur in celis (Duggan 438).

Several examples are found of excessive use of quotations,⁹ sometimes difficult to understand. As the writer of *Expectans* thinks that the king’s errors are mainly due to the wicked people around him, he tells the king to send away

⁹ The Bible and the *Decretum* are quoted often in both the Latin and the French letters (see *infra*), and there are, in the Latin letters, several correct quotations of Latin secular literature.

tun felun conseil.../ Qui te frea, ço criem, si parfunt avaler/ Que ja mais ne purras resurdre ne munter (Garnier 2858–2860 ; ‘(send away) your wicked counselors, who, I am afraid, cause you to fall so deep that you can never get up’).

The simple image of somebody sinking down so deep that he cannot come up has been decorated in the Latin letter by a quotation :

... expectaui ut... abscideretis... latera uestra praua, quorum... consilio iam fere lapsi estis in profundum (sed ueveor add. in the mss. CD) – quod absit ! – ne in profundum illud de quo dicitur « Peccator, cum uenerit in profundum contemnit » (Duggan 328).

The truncated quotation of Vulg. Prov. 18.3 is confusing to any reader who does not know the Proverbs by heart. Henry II must have relied on his clerics to have the missing passage (*sed sequitur eum ignominia et obprobrium*) filled in.

A quotation may render the entire text ambiguous. In *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket feels that Gilbert Foliot’s remark regarding his poor origins belittles his parents, and he answers *Ço ne devreit pas dire huem cristien, letrez,/ Religius, evesques* (Garnier 3421–3422). The Latin letter inserts here three words from Juvenal’s eighth satire, adding that they come from a pagan source « *Stemmata quid faciunt* » *ait gentilis poeta* (Duggan 432). The text continues *Quid hoc habet dicere Christianus, episcopus et religiosus ?* The addition has blurred the Latin text and it remains unclear what exactly is unfitting for a Christian and a bishop : belittling Thomas Becket’s parents or quoting pagan literature ?¹⁰

¹⁰ Juvenal’s satire ridicules people who boast about their ancestors’ brilliant exploits without feeling obliged to emulate them. – Pagan literature was not always accepted by the Church (cf. Decr. D 37 c 1 *Episcopus libros gentilium non legat*).

Quotations can damage the Latin syntax as well. *Desiderio* reminds the king that he should rule by controlling first himself (as his behavior is observed by his subjects), and thereafter others : he has to be mild towards some and strict towards most ; in French :

La grace Deu vos fist... coruner,/Pur ço vos devez mult constraindre e gouverner// Que vos puissiez as autres buen essample duner/ Car a vostre faisance volent tuit esgarder./ A tels i a suëf et dulz estre devez//E reddes as plusurs (Garnier 3076–3083).

Here, the Latin letter deems it appropriate to quote Claudian, but the syntax becomes difficult :

Nosse debetis uos Dei gratia regem esse ; primo quia vos ipsum regere debetis..., ut uestri exemplo ceteri prouocentur ad melius, iuxta illud sapientis, « Componitur orbis Regis ad exemplum »¹¹ ; secundario alios : hos demulcendo, alios puniendo... (Duggan 294).

The writer has tried to keep his sentence together by marking the two direct objects of *regere* with *primo* and *secundario*.

We study closer a lengthy and confusing passage, while we pay attention to the superfluous expressions in the Latin text. (The passage has also *Decretum* quotations : they will be examined *infra*.)

In the beginning of *Expectans*, the letter-writer says that he has expected, and daily prayed for the king's return to the Church. This beginning is quite similar in the two texts (Garnier 2855-2870 ;

¹¹ What follows in Claudian's *De IV Consulatu Honorii Augusti* : 300 *Nec sic inflectere sensus/ humanos edicta ualent, ut uita regentis*, has been left out – maybe this quotation was familiar to any young prince. Edward Grim's text leaves out *hos: Secundario, alios demulcendo, alios puniendo...* (Robertson, *Mat.* 2: 420).

Duggan 328). Thereafter the French text continues (we mark the three stanzas):

575 *Pur ço le di que mei qui dei suz Deu garder*

I tell this because, while I am the one who, under God, has to protect

L'iglise del reaume e les mesfaiz oster

the Church of the kingdom and take away the wrongs,

As essillié e fait hors del país aller

I have been driven into exile and made to leave the country by you,

Saint'iglise e les suens qu'i sunt mis, mesmener.

and you have had the Holy Church and her own (appointed) people ill-treated.

Jo l'ai mis en suffrance, que nel fis amender.

I have tolerated this without having it redressed.

576 *Por ço sui mult dolenz que tu as tant mespris*

I am very sad because you have done so many wrongs

Vers sainte mere iglise¹² e as suens qu'i sunt mis

against the holy Mother Church (=Canterbury) and her (appointed) members

Car jo part as mesfaiz, quant justise n'en fis,

for I myself take part in the misdeeds since I did not condemn them.

Qui justise est e juges, e il en est jolis,

If somebody is a judge and has the task to pass judgment, but is careless,

Il e li pechiere est en uël culpe asis.

he and the sinner are equally guilty.

577 *Saint'Esriture dit e sil testimonie*

The Holy Scripture says and bears witness to the fact

¹² In the French *Decretum* translation, *mere iglise* renders *metropolitana sedes* (e.g. ... *rectoresque ecclesiarum unum eundemque in psallendo teneant modum, quem metropolitana in sede cognouerint institutum* Decr. D 12 c 13 – *li gouverneur des eglises soient contraint... que il gardent cele meismes maniere de chanter qui est establee en la mere iglise* Fr Decr. D 12 c 13, l. 5). Likewise, *La sainte mere iglise de Sainte Ternité, // Restablisiez... en cele dignité // Qu'el' out as anceseurs* (Garnier 3166–3170) and T-L 5, 1513,29.

Que li consentanz est del mesfait en partie,
That a person who consents to a misdeed shares the guilt
Parkes¹³ cil quil deit faire, e puet, e nel chastie.

That is, the one who has the duty and power to chastise, and does not do it.

Car bien pert que cil ad el mesfait compaignie

So (car< QUA RE) it is obvious that such a person belongs to the evil-doers

Ki ne volt contre-ester a l'aperte folie.

who does not want to oppose to obvious folly.

578 Reis, men voil te voldreie plainement chastier

Sire, I would like to fully chastise/teach you ;

Pur ço t'ai fait mes lettres mult sovent enveier.

that is why I have often sent you letters (Garnier 2871–2886).

The text can be summed up : The sender, who is responsible for the English Church, explains this (i.e. the prayers for the king's return to the Church) referring to the fact that he who is responsible for the Church, was made to go to exile and the Church and the clergy were ill-treated by the king; the sender has tolerated the wrongs without having the situation corrected; now he brings to the king's attention especially those wrongs that have been acted on the archiepiscopal see of Canterbury. The writer regrets that he has not mentioned them or taken action against them before, as he feels guilty of the wrongs he did not condemn although it was his duty to

¹³ Walberg translates this *parkes* 'partant, par suite' (so also FEW 8, 212b), and DEAF 'c'est pourquoi', 'par suite'. *Parkes* seems to be limited to Garnier's text, where it is used twice in *Expectans* (2883 and 2915 *p. celui*) and once when Garnier quotes Thomas Becket (4904 *p. ço*); in all of these instances it precedes the phonetic group [ts], which would allow the analysis *par qu'es<t> cil*, etc. A fourth *parkes* (5682) before *la u* is translated 'surtout(?)' par Walberg.

do so. —From *Car jo part* on, the letter uses the French *Decretum* text and we will return to it (*infra*).

Here is the Latin text (from Duggan 330), which is practically the same in all manuscripts collated by Duggan. For the part to be analysed now, we give our *uerbatim* translation in segments (a–g), and underline and number the passages (1–6) that cannot be compared to anything in the French text :

a) *Et ecce inde est quod ecclesie Cantuariensis, cui Deus*

So it is, because <the care>¹⁴ for the Church of Canterbury to which God
b) *nostrum sacerdotium, licet indignum, uobis (te C, om. D) res humanas huius regni regentibus, ad presens deputauit, nos cura constringit,*

has assigned ¹ for the time being, our priesthood, ² albeit unworthy while you are ruling the human affairs of this kingdom, [the care] obliges us,

c) *eo maxime quod adhuc exilii incommoditate detineamur*

mainly because we are still held in the inconvenience of exile,

d) *maiestati uestre commonitorias, exhortatorias, correptorias et utinam ad plenum correctorias, destinare*

to send your majesty ³ warning, exhorting, reproaching and (I hope) fully correcting letters,

e) *ne excessuum uestrorum, si qui sunt (qui reuera sunt, unde non minimum dolemus,)*

so that <I would not be too neglectful> of your excesses, ⁴ if there are any (indeed there are, which makes us not little (= extremely) sad)

f) – *illorum maxime dico qui circa ecclesiam Dei et personas ecclesiasticas a uobis passim (nulla habita dignitatis seu persone reuerentia) aguntur–*

– especially of those, I say, that are carried out by you against God’s Church and ecclesiastical persons here and there ⁵ without any reverence for dignity or person–

¹⁴ In the Latin text *cura* ‘care’ comes considerably later, in the next segment. In the translation of that occurrence, we give [the care] in brackets.

g) *nimius dissimulator existam ne nimis negligens in anime mee discrimen appaream,*

[I would not be too neglectful], ⁶ nor seem to be overly remiss, to a point where I risk the welfare of my soul. (*Decretum* quotations will be discussed *infra*)

The elasticity of Latin syntax is tested by the syntagm *ecclesie Cantuariensis cura*, taken apart and found in segments a and b, and even more by the syntagm *excessuum uestrorum dissimulator* whose parts are found in e and g.

The first of the numbered and underlined passages states a self-evident fact ; the second is a version of a *captatio benevolentiae* formula ; the third gives redundant adjectives (the recipient knowing full well what kind of letters he may have received) ; the fourth is an out-of-place conditional clause that is somehow crossed over by what follows ; the fifth is gratuitous or misleading ; and the sixth repeats the danger of neglectfulness already stated, adding a hypocritical note about the welfare of the letter-writer's soul.

None of the passages imparts any new information, or makes the over-all text clearer. On the contrary, read without the 'secondary' bits underlined in the translation, the Latin text is less confusing:

Et ecce inde est quod ecclesie Cantuariensis, cui Deus nostrum sacerdotium deputauit, nos constringit, eo maxime quod adhuc exilii incommoditate detineamur, maiestati uestre litteras destinare, ne excessuum uestrorum, illorum maxime, dico, qui circa ecclesiam Dei et personas ecclesiasticas a uobis passim aguntur, nimius dissimulator existam. « Facientis proculdubio culpam habet, qui quod debet corrigere, negligit emendare » .

Easy to delete (without changing the remaining text, except replacing *comminatorias*, etc., by *litteras*), the 'secondary' bits give

the impression of being easily inserted additions. It is remarkable that all Latin manuscripts have them.

This comparison of the Latin with the French text shows, except for the numerous additions in the Latin text, also some other differences between the texts : in Latin, the writer is responsible for the see of Canterbury, but in French he is the *primas*, responsible for the Church of the entire kingdom (*L'iglise del reaume*), although he now brings the attack on Canterbury to the king's attention; in Latin, the writer's sending (many) letters is placed in the middle of the quoted passage, whereas in our French clip, the corresponding statement is found at the end (and belonging metrically to the next stanza where the writer moves on to a discussion about the relationship of secular and ecclesiastical powers). In the Latin text the author's plural (*we*) gives way to an everyday singular (*I*) also in the middle of the passage (*nos cura... constringit... dolemus vs. dico... existam*). Could this be a sign of some disturbance in the finalizing stage of the official Latin letter?

In the above passages, is Garnier's French text a translation of the Latin text? Would Garnier have been able to recognize and to eliminate any redundant elements in a Latin sentence in order to express, in French, the true meaning of the author? Would he have been able to correct a sentence damaged by quotations in order to give a clear French translation of it? It would have been a herculean task since the Latin text is so over-saturated with these secondary elements.

2. Other differences

A letter normally gives some information about the sender's relationship to the recipient, as the writer plans his missives taking into account what the other person might already know about the subject matter at hand, in order to give pertinent and interesting information and to avoid repetitions.

The letter *Desiderio* divides the Christian society into two orders, clergy and laymen, Garnier adding that the prelates take care of 'God's part', *La cure unt li prelat de la part Deu conquire* (Garnier 3114; Short's transl. : 'the prelates have acquired the task of caring for the people on behalf of God') and the king and other baronage having secular people and laws in their guardianship (Garnier 3121–3123). The Latin *Desiderio* text feels the need to identify the ranks of the governing entities :

In clero sunt apostoli, apostolici uiri, episcopi, et ceteri doctores ecclesie and In populo sunt reges, principes, duces, comites, et alie potestates (Duggan 296)

in a letter addressed to Henry II who, one may safely assume, knew who belonged to his baronage. Here, the Latin letter sounds awkward.

When answering, in *Mirandum*, Gilbert Foliot's complaint about the excommunications of Richard of Ilchester, bishop of Salisbury, and of John of Oxford his (irregularly appointed) dean, Garnier's text does not use any names or other identifications :

Des deus que j'ai, ço diz, des cristiens sevré! A tort... mais tut a dreit ! – as meü le pensé... (Garnier 3501–3502; 'you are worried about the two whom I

excommunicated, as you say, wrongly... but [I say, on the contrary] quite lawfully !...’)

in contrast to the Latin text :

In Saresberiensem episcopum, et Iohannem de Oxenefordia, non decanum, ut dicis, sed decanatus inuasorem, me preiudicio abusum calumpniaris... Et motum te dicis (Duggan 436).

Garnier’s verse seems to go back to a text intended to be read by Gilbert Foliot, as an answer to Foliot’s own letter.¹⁵ The recipient is sure to know whom *Des deus* ‘regarding the two’ refers to. This French text seems to be more personal and spontaneous than the official Latin letter where the excommunicated are identified.

Is it likely that Garnier would have been skillful enough to create an illusion of spontaneity by leaving out details the recipient must have known ? Rather, it seems that these details absent in the French text, have been added *for the record* into the official Latin text.

For Garnier to be the translator of a Latin letter, he is not expected to add new information to it. Indeed, compared with the Latin letters, the French letters have barely any gratuitous additions and filler lines in the five-line stanzas are very rare.

In contrast, the following examples may rather illustrate a lacuna in the Latin text :

¹⁵ (Quoting from *Que uestro pater* :) *Movet quidem nos quod in fratrem nostrum, domnum Saresberiensem episcopum et decanum eiusdem prepostere... Nuper actum audiivimus...* (Duggan 380).

In *Desiderio*, after the presentation of the two ‘orders’ of the Church, *En dous ordres de gent est faite saint’eglise/Del pueple e del clergie est faite e asise* (Garnier 3111–3112), I think that Garnier’s line 3113 *E par dreit aünie est en ceste devise* ‘and rightfully united in this separation’ is important; in fact, it seems to reflect Thomas Becket’s *Decretum*-inspired endeavor to create peace inside the Church by assigning their clearly defined areas of competence to the two judicial systems, secular and ecclesiastical.¹⁶ The line has no equivalent in the Latin text (Duggan 296).

At the very end of the letter *Mirandum* Thomas Becket underlines the king’s duties towards the Church, in the French text :

A ço fait Deus le rei sur le regne establir

For this does God establish the king to rule over the kingdom

Qu’il deit la peis que Deus nus tramet, maintenir.

That he shall maintain the peace that God gives us.

Altrement ne puet pas li reis aveir salu

Otherwise the king cannot be saved

Pur tute sa grant force ne pur sa grant vertu

For all of his great force and his great strength

Nis se tuit li regne erent par li sul maintenu.

Even if he would hold all kingdoms in his hand (Garnier 3549);

and in the Latin text :

¹⁶ I take *devise* in its primary signification ‘separation’ (T-L 2, 1874, 39). Cf. the very beginning of *Decretum* : *Humanum genus duobus regitur, naturali uidelicet iure et moribus* and *Decr. D 1 c 1 Omnes leges aut diuinae sunt, aut humanae. Diuinae natura, humanae moribus constant.* Both Thomas and Short translate *devise* by ‘manner’ (in accordance to T-L 2, 1878, 29).

Ad hoc enim uocatus est, et in hoc ipsum temporalis regni pax et magnificentia (de qua nos communes, words adding a reference to Foliot's letter), ministratur ei de celo. Alioquin non saluatur rex per multam uirtutem suam, etsi subdantur ei regna et inclinentur nationes (440; Duggan's transl. 'To this, indeed was he called, and for this, the peace and magnificence of the temporal kingdom, about which you remind us, is given to him from heaven. Otherwise the king will not be saved by his great strength, even though realms are subject to him and nations bow before him').

The Latin text with its *ad hoc uocatus* is not quite clear. What was the king called for? The immediately-preceding text expresses a wish and a warning: first the wish that the king might act like the good emperor Constantine who, as it is told even earlier, refused to examine accused priests; thereafter a warning reference to an Old Testament passage that prescribes the death penalty to whoever out of pride does not listen to the priest or the judge (in the Latin letter, Vulg. Deut. 17.12 is quoted *uerbatim*). So what does *ad hoc uocatus est* refer to? According to the Latin text only to choose between the imitation of Constantine and the death penalty, but according to the French letter, God gives a ruler his kingdom *Qu'il deit la peis que Deus nus tramet, maintenir* in order for him to maintain God-given peace. As maintaining the peace is traditionally the king's most important duty,¹⁷ one asks whether there is a mistake in the (transmission of the) Latin letter.

¹⁷ The first paragraph in *Leis Willelme*, the earliest Anglo-Norman law text (from mid-twelfth century) is *Ceo est a saver, pais a seinte iglise* (Liebermann I, 1903: 492). See also *Charta Henrici I Coronati*, 1 (ibid. 521); Edw. the Confessors laws, 1 (ibid. 628).

Is it probable that Garnier would have recognized the unclear passages in the Latin text to correct them ?

For Garnier to be the translator of the Latin letters, the Latin letters would have to precede Garnier's text. Is this always unquestionable ?

In *Expectans*, after presenting the exemplary punishments of some Old Testament princes who in their pride usurped sacerdotal privileges, Garnier resumes :

Reis, suëf se chastie qui d'auitruï se chastie ;/ Cele parole as tu en plusurs lius oïe
(Garnier 2976–2677)

and the Latin *Expectans* :

Rex, prouerbialiter celebre est, castigatus de alterius infortunio melius sibi prospicit.
'*Nam sua res agitur paries cum proximus ardet*' (Duggan 336) .

Garnier uses first a well-known French proverb (Short's translation : 'It is a pleasant lesson to learn by others' mistakes' ; see J. Morawski 1925, nr. 2265) and the Latin text gives a translation of a part of this French proverb (*castigatus de alterius infortunio* corresponds to *qui d'auitruï se chastie*) followed by *melius sibi prospicit*, and then, slightly modified, a Latin proverb, known from Horace.¹⁸ Here, the Latin text seems to depend on the French text and not vice versa.

¹⁸ H. WALTHER (*Lateinische Sprichwörter und Sentenzen des Mittelalters*, 1963-1967, Göttingen, Vandenhoech & Ruprecht) gives under 2469b a better

After comparing the French and the Latin letters, we find it highly unlikely that Garnier translated the French letters from the Latin ones. The French letters' clear and simple language can hardly be explained by the Latin text, plagued by redundancies and quotations. The French letters may even preserve a more spontaneous (omission of details known to the recipient) and correct (regarding the king's calling) text than the Latin ones. We rather think that Garnier versified pre-existing French letters.

TWO PARALLEL SETS OF LETTERS, FRENCH AND LATIN ?

In her introduction, Anne Duggan draws attention to the fact that members of the secretarial staff at Thomas Becket's exile court could prepare parallel letters "Herbert (de Bosham) transmits three versions of *Fraternitatis uestre*... The first two were drafted respectively by himself and Master Lombard, but both were set aside in favour of the third... for which no individual author has been recorded" (2000: xxiv). Could there have been parallel letters written in French?

Some details in the French letters, versified by Garnier, make us think that they were originally written by an 'insider', a person who had access to the general plan of the letter and the material suggested (references, quotations) to be used in it, but also, the liberty to use the material independently.

equivalent to the French proverb: *Castigat pena sese prudens aliena*, a proverb quoted from John Rylands Library, Latin Ms. 394.

The unusual greeting (noun + infinitive¹⁹) in the French *Expectans*

... *saluz et ovrer si/ Qu'il guerpisse e ament tuz les mals qu'a fait ci* (Garnier 2854–2855; Short's free translation: 'greetings and may he act in such a way that he forsake and make amends for all the wrongs that he has done in his life')

expresses in a playful (?) way the wish that Henry II might mend his ways (lit. 'greetings and to act so that...'). Latin *Expectans* juxtaposes two nouns (in accusative)

... *salutem et ueram cum emendatione penitentiam* (Duggan 2000 : 328).

Browsing through the Latin greetings in Duggan's vol. 1, I found that this latter type was very frequently used (e.g. *s. et spiritum consolationis*; *s. et... benedictionem*), and that the letter-writer's greeting was also quite often expressed, without *salutem*, by an infinitive that does not depend on a finite verb. Thomas Becket may even give a double infinitive as a greeting:

Thomas... Saresberiensis episcopo uisis litteris nostris statim resipiscere a malo et de cetero constantius facere bonum (Duggan 2000: 302; Duggan's translation '... when he sees this letter, desist from wrongdoing and for the future more constantly do good')

or resume the contents of his letter in the infinitive:

¹⁹ Comparable uses for nominalized infinitive can be found in Old French (Buridant 2000: § 252).

Thomas... *Galfrido inobedienti archidiacono Cantuarie, consultius sibi prospicere propter inobedientiam* (Duggan 2000: 490; Duggan's translation 'to Geoffrey, disobedient archdeacon of Canterbury, look out for himself more carefully because of disobedience').

The construction *salutem et* + infinitive, rather the exception in other men's letters: *s. et bene semper ualere* (anon. to Thomas Becket, Duggan 2000: 96); *s. et confortari in eo qui dissipat consilia...* (John of Salesbury to Thomas Becket, Duggan 2000: 468), was found several times in letters by Thomas Becket:

s. et per omnia bene facere (Duggan 2000: 266); *s. et in spiritu mansuetudinis congregare dispersos Israel* (358); *s. et id agere quod nondum agunt* (388); *s. et per omnia benefacere* (440); *s. et in fortitudine patientie consolationem Domini fiducialiter expectare* (674); *s. et sic agere ut uiuat in Domino* (722),

although not in those versified by Garnier. — The French *saluz et orrer...* could indeed indicate that even the writer of the French letters belonged to the original letter-writing team and was using Thomas Becket's particular jargon.

We continue by studying such quotations or literary loans as are found in both the French and the Latin letters: is the common material used in in the same way ?

1. *Bible quotations.*

It has to be kept in mind that the entire Bible text was not yet translated into French.

A passage in *Desiderio*, Garnier's lines 3101–3105, derives the origin of the Church from the passion story, exhorting the letter's royal recipient to follow in the Lord's footsteps; Garnier's lines 3105–3110 tell that whoever wants to partake in heavenly glory, has to keep his body in severe discipline for the love of God :

Li covient estre el cors, pur amur Deu, martir (Garnier 3107) and *La volenté del cors e les eises guerpír/ Ensi cum sainz Pols dist : Pur Deu devum murir,/Se od li volum vivre, e pur li mort suffrir* (3108–3110; 'leave the body's wishes and comforts, like St Paul says : We have to die for God if we wish to live with him...').

Rather than quoting a passage of Saint Paul (the reference is very general and could direct the reader to Vulg. 1 Cor. 4. 11-16, or to 2 Cor.4,10-11, or to 2 Tim. 2,11-12), the French letter uses the apostle's teachings.

In contrast, the Latin letter-writer does not use the Pauline text when counseling the king. After it is said that Christ suffered *nobis relinquens exemplum ut sequamur uestigia eius*, there is no practical advice for an everyday *imitatio Christi*, comparable to *La volenté del cors e les eises guerpír* in Garnier's text. Instead of a general reference to Saint Paul, the Latin text

Vnde et dicit Apostolus : Si compatimur ei, et conregnabimus. Si commorimur, et conresurgemus (Duggan 296; Duggan's transl. '...If we suffer with him, we shall reign with him. If we die with him, we shall rise with him')

provides a quotation combining Vulg. Rom. 8,17 and 2 Tim. 2,11-12 that, read by a layman, seems to prepare him for martyrdom proper.

The letter *Mirandum* states that God can use the word ‘god’ for priests. This bold statement is backed up by many quotations very clearly visible in the Latin text (that we quote from Duggan 438):

Sic enim dicit, ‘Ego dixi, dii estis, et filii Excelsi omnes’ (Vulg./LXX Ps. 81,6) ; et ad Moysen, ‘Constitui te deum Pharaonis’ (Vulg. Exod. 7, 1), et ‘Diis non detrahes’ (Vulg.Exod. 22,28); id est, sacerdotibus. Et de eo qui iuraturus erat, loquens per Moysen ait : ‘Applica illum ad Deos,’ (Vulg. Exod. 22,8 ; quotation in Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41) id est, ad sacerdotes. Nec presumat dominus noster iudices suos uelle iudicare. Terrenis enim potestatibus non sunt commisse claves regni celorum, sed sacerdotio. Inde scriptum est, ‘Labia sacerdotis custodient scientiam, et legem requirent ab ore eius, quia angelus Domini exercituum est.’ (Vulg. Mal. 2, 7, quoted in Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41) Paulus etiam dicit, ‘Nonne angelos iudicabimus ? Quanto magis homines ?’ (cf. Vulg. 1 Cor. 6,3).

The quotations are less conspicuous and less correct in Garnier’s verse :

Deus les apele ‘Deu’, ço trovum el Psaltier. (Correct identification)

God calls them gods – that we find in the Psalter.

Le prophete fist Deus sur Pharaun drezier ; (Passage probably not recognized)

God did raise the prophet over Pharaoh ;

Nis mesparler des clers rove Deus a laissier. (Correct interpretation)

God asks us even to avoid all bad talk about clerics. (Fr.Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41, 6 *tu ne detreras pas as diex*)

Un Gïeu qui aveit per Moysen juré

A Jew who had sworn by Moses

Aveit um as proveires pur cel pechié mené. (Passage not recognized)

was taken to the priests for this sin.

« Amenez le as Deus », fait li Reis de bunté. (Quotation recognized)

The King of Mercy (= goodness) says « Take him to the priests ». (Fr.Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41, 1.6 *Amaine le as diex*)

De Deu sunt li proveire ‘Deu’ dit e apelé,

The priests are called ‘gods’ after God,

Car sur les genz sunt mis el liu Deu e sacré. (Letter-writer's addition)

since they are put over people in God's place and consecrated.

Ne puet li reis de cels faire nul jugement

The king cannot judge those

Ki lui deivent e poent jugier veraïement.

who have the duty and the power to pass rightful judgment over him.

« *Les levres del proveire sunt garde d'escient,* (Quotation recognized)

The priest's lips are guardians of knowledge, (Fr. Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41, l.7 *Les levres as provoires gardent escience*)

Li prestre est angeles Deu ». (Quotation recognized)

the priest is God's messenger ». (Fr. Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41, l. 8... *il est angres Damledieu*)

Ço dit Pols qui ne ment :

St. Paul who does not lie says this :

Nus jugerum les angeles, les genz meesmement. » (Quoted from memory)

« We will judge angels, and especially²⁰ people ».

A prince terrien ne volt ainc Deus baillier

God did not want to give to a secular prince

Les clefs del ciel, qui poent lier e deslier,

the keys of heaven that can bind and unbind,

Mes as ordenez fait sa poesté traitier.

but He lets the ordained exercise His power (Garnier 3518–3533).

We see that the French letter-writer quotes Saint Paul correctly (albeit not from the Vulgate, maybe from memory ?), but that he masters only fragments of Old Testament, namely the Psalms and the passages quoted in the *Decretum*. More learned, the person writing the Latin letters gives all Bible quotations correctly, the Pauline passages maybe from memory (not from the Vulgate).

²⁰ This *meesmement* is most likely <MAXIMAMENTE (T-L 5, 881,40), and not <*METIPSIMAMENTE (T-L 5,1351,19).

Le prophete fist Deus sur Pharaun drecier may use the word *prophete* for Moses (so in Vulg. Deut. 34,10) or it may go back to a vague reference to Vulg. Exod. 7, 1 *dixitque Dominus ad Mosen : Ecce constitui te Deum Pharaonis ; Aaron frater tuus erit propheta tuus* (of which the Latin *Mirandum* quotes the beginning).

Garnier's erroneous text *Un Gieu qui aveit per Moÿsen juré/ Aveit um as proveires pur cel pechié mené./» Amenez le as Deus », fait li Reis de bunté* needs an explanation. The Latin *Mirandum* text writes *de eo qui iuraturus erat, loquens per Moysen, ait « Applica illum ad deos »* (Duggan 438). Referring to Vulg. Exod. 22,8²¹ neither text goes back to the *Decretum* (Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41 *nam et ad*²² *Moysen de eo qui ad iuramentum deducendus est, dicitur - Fr. Decr. C 11 q 1 c 41, l. 5 L'on dit a Moyses de celui qui doit estre amenez a serment*). While Garnier's verse (*qui aveit per Moÿsen juré*) talks about something that has happened, the Latin *Mirandum* gives a precept for the future, as do the two *Decretum* texts. It seems that the Latin text is closer to the original. Indeed *aveit juré* could even be explained by *iuraturus erat*²³ provided that *iuraturus* was written

²¹ The Exodus passage describes a situation where somebody is in charge of an item belonging to another person and this item is stolen while in his charge: *si latet* (scil. *fur* 'if the thief cannot be found'), *dominus domus* (the lord of the house who was in charge of the stolen item) *adplicabitur ad deos et iurabit quod non extenderit manum in proximi sui ad perpetranda fraudem*.

²² Editio Romana has *per* instead of *ad*.

²³ Similarly Thomas 2002, comm. ad l. – Thomas adds one more interpretation to the passage; the text « peut faire sens, si on traduit les plus-que-parfaits de 3521–2 par des imparfaits. D'autant que 'Tout blasphème du nom de Moïse était passible de mort' ». This appealing interpretation would imply a good mastery of ancient Jewish culture that we hesitate to attribute to the French letter-writer.

with an *ur* abbreviation (*iurat^{us}*) so small that the French letter-writer did not notice it. I am tempted to reconstruct the unknown original for this passage: **de eo qui iurat^{us} erat per Moysen ait*. It could have been misread and translated **De celui qui a veit juré per Moysen dist Il* (and then (mis)interpreted – by Garnier ?– to give birth to this imaginary story of the Jew who had sworn ‘by Moses’). The Latin letter-writer, in turn, who would have recognized the passage and its *ur* abbreviation, seems have added *loquens* into the text, in order to make sure that *per Moysen* is understood as an indication of the source text (i.e. Exodus, the 2 Book of Moses) of the passage, and not the ‘saint’ by whom one could take an oath.

Our comparison of the letter-writers’ Bible quotations shows that the French letter-writer knows the Pauline letters, but is not very familiar with the Old Testament: he knows the Psalms and recognizes fragments of the Old Testament indirectly, via the *Decretum* and maybe other texts. More learned, the person writing the Latin letters gives all Bible quotations correctly; the Pauline passages are quoted from memory.

The letter-writers are distinguished, not only by the number of correct Bible quotations, but also by the use of the passages. The more learned Latin letter-writer does not interpret or develop any quotation. The less learned French letter-writer cares for his audience: he explains peculiar details in the quotation (reason for the particular use of the word ‘god’, e.g.) or rewords a quotation to make it easier to understand (no bad talk about clerics); earlier, we saw (*supra*) him work the teachings of Saint Paul into his own text, rather than just quoting them.

2. *Biblical images*

Alongside quotations, the letters use biblical images. They may be interpreted differently in the French and Latin letters, although correctly in both versions. In *Expectans*, a rod belonging to God (Lat. *virga* /OFr. *verge*) is taken in the French letters as an attribute of God the judge, according to LXX Ps. 44, 7-8, but in the Latin letters as an image of God's fury and revenge, according to Vulg. Is. 10, 5 (*infra*). In *Mirandum*, the expression *corpus Christi / le cors Jesu Crist* 'Christ's body' taken as a Pauline metaphor (cf. 1 Cor. 12, 27) in the French letters, but literally, 'Jesus of Nazareth's physical body', in the Latin letters (*infra*).

3. *Decretum* quotations.

The *Decretum* seems to have been available in both Latin and French. If the writer of the Latin letter quotes a passage of Gratian's *Decretum*, the French letter-writer uses the same passage according to the French translation of the *Decretum*. In this way, the Latin and French letters give parallel examples of canon passages.

Decretum passages can be quoted from the beginning, middle or end of a canon and neither the Latin nor the French quotation has any 'chapter' markings²⁴ that would direct their reader to the

²⁴ In the Latin *Decretum* text of Ludwig XIV:2 (1170-1180) and in the French *Decretum* translation conserved in Brussels, BR 9084 (ca. 1280) only the *Distinctiones*, *Causae*, and *Quaestiones* are marked with numerals. In Brussels, BR

Decretum unit (e.g. *causa, quaestio*) from which they are taken ; and the letters do not follow any particular order when using canon law passages. The *Decretum* passages randomly used in these parallel quotations represent the first half of the *Decretum* text, through Causa 12 at least (a potential text corpus of more than 400 modern book pages).

In a passage of *Expectans* (after the letter-writer's complaint about damages caused to the Church, analysed *supra*) both letters seem to be using D 86 c 3 and D 83 c 3.

I present the Latin and French passages separately giving in both cases the appropriate *Decretum* text right after the letter text. In the Latin letter text, I have underlined *debeant*, in the French letter text, *deit* : the addition of the verb *debere, devoir* is the only modification to the *Decretum* text that the Latin and French letters have in common. The Latin letter quotes the *Decretum* practically without changes (the very same bold text presents itself twice) :

« *Facientis proculdubio culpam habet, qui quod debet corrigere, negligit emendare* ». *Scriptum quippe est, « Non solum qui faciunt, sed etiam qui consentiunt, participes iudicantur* ». *Consentiunt quidem, qui cum possint et debeant, non resistunt, uel saltem redarguunt. Error enim, cui non resistitur, approbatur ; et ueritas, cum minime defensatur, opprimitur. Nec caret occulte societatis scrupulo, qui desinit obuiare manifesto facinori* » (Duggan 330 ; Duggan's transl. 'Without any doubt, he is at fault who neglects to correct what he should correct. Inasmuch as it is written, « Not only they who do wrong, but also they who agree to it are judged to be participants ». And they indeed consent, who

9084, the canons are marked with their Latin *incipits*, before the beginning of the French canon text.

do not resist or at least censure the deed, when they can and should. In fact, an error which is not opposed is approved, and when truth is not defended, it is overthrown. Nor is the one who ceases opposing an obvious crime free from the suspicion of secret complicity.’)

COMPARE TO:

Decr. D 86 c 3 **Facientis proculdubio culpam habet, qui quod potest corrigere, negligit emendare. Scriptum quippe est » Non solum qui faciunt, sed etiam qui consentiunt participes iudicantur ».**

Decr. D 83 c 3 **Error, cui non resistitur, approbatur, et ueritas, cum minime defensatur, obprimitur.** Negligere quippe, cum possis perturbare peruersos, nihil est aliud quam fouere. **Nec caret scrupulo societatis occultae, qui manifesto facinori desinit obuiare.**

The French text uses only some passages of the *Decretum* text, (I bar the text that is not used), but the passages that are used are worked into the letter :

Car jo part as mesfaiz, quant justise n'en fis,

For I myself take part in the misdeeds since I did not condemn them.

Qui justise est e juges, e il en est jolis,

If somebody is a judge and has the task to pass judgment, but is careless,

Il e li pechiere est en uël culpe asis.

he and the sinner are equally guilty.

Saint'Esripture dit e sil testimonie

The Holy Scripture says and bears witness to the fact

Que li consentanz est del mesfait en partie,

that a person who consents to a misdeed shares the guilt,

Parques cil quil deit faire, e puet, e nel chastie.

that is, the one who has the duty and power to chastise, and does not do

it.

Car bien pert que cil ad el mesfait compaignie

So (car < QUA RE ‘rebus sic stantibus’) it is obvious that such a person belongs to the evil-doers

Ki ne volt contre-ester a l’aperte folie.

who does not want to oppose to obvious folly. (Garnier 2879–2882)

COMPARE TO:

Fr. Decr. D 86 c 3, l. 2 Cil qui est negligenz d’amender ce que il puet chastier est autresi corpables comme se il eust fet le mesfet, car il est escrit : » ~~Non pas tant seulement cil qui font le fet, mes~~ cil qui s’i consentent en sont parçonnier ».

Fr. Decr. D 83 c 3, l. 3 ~~Il se consent a l’erreur qui ne va encontre et la verité dechiet quant el n’est desfandue.~~ Se tu despiz a troubler les mauvés quant tu le puez fere, tu fez autresi comme se tu les sostenoies. Et cil n’est pas sanz sopeçon de compaignie reposte qui ne contredit le mesfez qui est aperz.

In the French text, the letter-writer projects the *Decretum* quotations into his own situation (*Jo part* ‘I take part’ ; *Qui justice est e juges* ‘the one who is judge’... an archbishop has the duty to pass judgment). Even the definition of consenting persons (Lat. *consentiunt*, plural, as in the *Decretum* texts) is given in singular as if continuing the description of a negligent judge. The addition of the verb *deberet/ devoir*, creates the juxtaposition of ‘power’ and ‘duty’, (Lat. *cum possint et debeant* ; Fr. *deit faire e puet*) both inherent in the position of a judge. The non-function of a person facing obvious criminals is described in the French letter *qui ne volt contre-ester* which makes the lack of action voluntary, and thereby a sin comparable to the accused evil-doer’s more concrete misdeed, while the Latin *desinit obuiare* could simply mean that the person is tired and takes a pause.

The Latin letter-writer leaves the interpretation of the quotations to the reader, the French letter-writer uses them as a part of his own message, omitting repetitions and generalisations.

The following example illustrates the letter-writers' different treatments of a problematic *Decretum* passage :

Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41 *Sicut ergo Achaz* (var. given by Friedberg : *Agab, Agaz, Agatt, Agad*) *a Domino lepra percussus est, qui sacerdotum offitia usurpare uoluit*
is faithfully translated in

Fr. Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41, l.40 *Autresi comme Diex feri Achaz de lepre, por ce que*²⁵
il volt entreprendre l'office as provoires.

The information given in this passage in all medieval *Decretum* manuscripts is wrong. *Achaz* –whatever the spelling of the name – did not usurp the privileges of a high priest nor did he contract leprosy (see Vulg. 4 Reg. 16, 1-20 and 2 Par. 28, 16-27)²⁶. According to the Vulgate, those were Ozias' crime and punishment:

²⁵ We have not found the corresponding Latin *quia* in medieval manuscripts. Friedberg, comm. ad l., gives it from the Editio Romana.

²⁶ The biblical *Ahaz, filius Ioatham* (Vulg. 4 Reg. 16,1), although never a Temple intruder and never a leper, is not free from incense-related sin. This king followed some heathen rites when *adolebat incensum in excelsis et in collibus et sub omni ligno frondoso* (4 Reg. 16.4) or according to the Chronicles *sacrificabat quoque et thymiama succendabat in excelsis et in collibus et sub omni ligno frondoso* (2 Par. 28, 4) or the QLR *é offríd éncéns á deáble el val de Gehennón é fist sacrefices é encéns offríd ás munz é partút la ú arbre bien fuillie truvad é ki umbre delitable jetad* (2 Chr. 28, 3; Curtius 207).

iratusque est Ozias et tenens in manu turibulum ut adoleret incensum minabatur sacerdotibus. Statimque orta est lepra in fronte eius coram sacerdotibus in domo Domini super altare thymiatis. Cumque respexisset eum Azarias pontifex et omnes reliqui sacerdotes, uiderunt lepram in fronte eius et festinato expulerunt eum... Fuit igitur Ozias rex leprosus usque ad diem mortis suae et habitauit in domo separata plenus lepra ob quam eiectus fuerat de domo Domini... regnauitque Ioatham filius eius pro eo (Vulg. 2 Par 26.19–21).

Both letters *Expectans*, Latin and French, quote Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41, but tell about king Ozias before presenting Achaz. Ozias carries incense and goes to sacrifice on the main altar. At that moment, leprosy appears on his forehead and he is thrown out of the Temple by the priests.

The Latin *Expectans* follows the Vulgate:

Ozie... regis... adeo cor eleuatum est... ut spreta Domini reuerantia usurpare sibi uoluerit quod sui officii non erat sed sacerdotum, id est, adholere incensum super altare Domini. Et ob hoc a Domino lepra percussus est et eiectus per manus sacerdotum a templo Domini, et sic mansit usque ad diem mortis sue, plenus lepra, ob quam eiectus fuerat de domo Domini (Duggan 334)

taking the syntagm *plenus lepra* directly from the Vulgate. After this comes a generalizing statement that God has reduced to nothing the wealth of many mighty kings *presumentes rebellare Deo in suis ministeriis*, and then, a few lines later, notwithstanding its wrong information, comes the *Decretum* passage:

Rex quoque Acas, quoniam et ipse officium sacerdotale usurpauit, similiter a Domino lepra percussus est (Duggan 336).

In the Latin *Expectans*, the Ozias story and the following erroneous *Decretum* quotation about Achaz are loosely connected by *similiter* and even more so by the syntagms *usurpare officium* and *lepra percussus* taken from the Achaz passage in Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41, but developed and used in *Expectans* already in the Ozias passage. The correctness of the *Decretum* passage is not questioned.

Likewise, the French letter text comes in two parts :

E li reis Ozias...!!!! Del saint encens porter el temple s'enhardi/ Deus s'en ert cureciez, de liepre le feri./Par les ordenez Deu qu'i furent establi,/Fu getez hors del temple.../Meseaus fu e lieprus tuz les jors qu'il vesqui (Garnier 2951–2960)

and, after a stanza stating that rebellious kings often see their wealth taken away by God,

Achaz le mestier Deu ensement envai,/Encensa cum evesque in domo Domini. / Reis esteit, e evesques voleit estre altres. / Deus s'en esteit irez, de liepre le covri./ Meseaus fu e degez...(Garnier 2966–2970).

The author of the French letter *Expectans* seems to know that the *Achaz* passage transmitted in Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41 should be not only preceded by the biblical Ozias story but also corrected with the help of it. Consequently, he lets Achaz take the blame of some of Ozias's misdeeds. He splits in half the 'criminal record' of the biblical king Ozias, giving both Ozias and Achaz their shares. Ozias is punished by leprosy *Del saint encens porter* for carrying incense, as the Vulgate describes him *tenens in manu turibulum*. Achaz gets his punishment when he already is burning incense on the altar: *Encensa... in domo Domini* refers to the same situation as the

expression *in domo Domini super altare thymiatis*, found in the Ozias story in the Vulgate. The leprosy plights of both Ozias and Achaz repeat expressions used in the Vulgate. Ozias is found *lepreus* in Garnier's text as he is found *leprosus* in the Vulgate. As Achaz stands at the altar, he receives his immediate punishment, in Garnier's text *Deus... de liepre le covri*, like Ozias in the Vulgate text: *orta est lepra in fronte eius*. – The French letter-writer leaves the Latin *in domo Domini* – taken from the Ozias story of the Vulgate – as an indication of the source text used for his redactional work on Achaz. This edited Achaz story is given after the biblical Ozias story, and (after the reference to the fate of the other rebellious kings) as a continuation to it, marked by *ensement* ('so', 'similarly', T-L 3, 524, 22 and 31).

How could the French letter-writer have learned that *Achaz* should be corrected by *Ozias*? Although his Bible quotations (*supra*) show that he was no Old Testament scholar, he may still have recognized the story of a king's sacrilegious behavior and its punishment by leprosy from the then recent Anglo-Norman *Quatre Livre des Reis*. In that book, the passage catches the reader's attention because of a name confusion.

Instead of *Ozias*, the king's name is *Achazies*, e.g. *Li rois Achazies fist tours lever en Jerusalem* (QLR 4, 26,9; Curtius 204, cf. *Aedificauitque Ozias tures in Hierusalem* in Vulg. 2 Par. 26,9); or, more often, *Azarias*. However, in the Vulgate (2 Par. 26, 17 and 20), *Azarias* is the name of the high priest opposing the sacrilegious king and this is the case also in the QLR, where the dispute between the two *Azarias* makes the passage very difficult to understand: *Azarias li evesches* (QLR 2 Chr., 26,17; Curtius 205); *A tant le ferid liepre en son vis... Cume cõ vit li evêshes Azarie é li pruvêire, chalt pas le butèrent fors del temple* (QLR 2

Chr.,26, 20; Curtius 205; ‘Then the leprosy ‘hit him in the face’... When the bishop A. and the priests saw this, they pushed him quickly out from the temple’; *Li reis Azarías murut... mesels fud ; e ses fiz Joathan regnad pur lui* (QLR 2 Chr., 26, 23; Curtius 205, cf. *dormiuitque Ozias... leprosus, regnavitque Ioatham filius eius pro eo* in Vulg. 2 Par. 26, 23).²⁷

This confusion in one short passage prompts any serious reader to open the corresponding books of the Vulgate to find the sacrilegious king’s proper name, and the writer of the French letter may have done just that. He may also have been reminded of it by John of Salisbury’s *Policraticus* (dated to 1159), from which Duggan (2000: 335, note 20) quotes *Imitantur plurimi Oziam sacerdotalia praesumentes, sed lepram eius paucissimi erubescunt* (viii, 22).

If the letter-writer recognized the flaw in the *Decretum* passage (Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41), why did he not simply omit the name *Achaz*, rather than try to justify its use as an alternative name of *Ozias*? Maybe because the name *Achaz* given in the *Decretum* is so close to *Achazies*, the other of *Ozias*’s names in the *Quatre Livre des Reis*. Or maybe also because of the letter-writer’s respect for the authority of *Decretum*, even if he re-edits the contents of the passage trying to reconcile the *Decretum* and the Bible: in the *Decretum* tradition, as shown in the apparatuses of Friedberg, the name *Achaz* in Decr. C 2 q 7 c 41 was corrected into *Ozias* only in the Renaissance.

²⁷ Duggan 336, note 21, observes that the king, son of Amasias and father of Ioatham, called *Ozias* in Vulg. 2 Par. 26, bears the name *Azarias* in Vulg. 4 Reg. 15. – He contacts the leprosy (4.Reg. 15,4) for allowing his people to burn incense on ‘high places’ (old heathen offering sites?), although he does not seem to have participated in their offerings himself. In 4 Reg. 15, the name *Azarias* does not cause any confusion, since there is nobody else by the same name in the passage.

I have argued that the « Getty Gratian », J. Paul Getty, Ms. Ludwig XIV :2, could be a copy of a manuscript used by Thomas Becket and his circle of learned men for their study of canon law (recently in Löfstedt 2015 :213-214). Adjacent to C 2 q 7 c 41 in Ludwig XIV :2 there are two marginal notes, roughly parallel to the king's name (in this manuscript *Achab* instead of *Achaz*): *in paralipoñ* and *in libro regum*, pointing to the two biblical texts (*Liber Paralipomenon* (the Chronicles) and *Libri Regum* (2 Books of Samuel and 2 Books of Kings = 4 Books of Kings) that can correct the information. It is worth noticing that a correction of sorts has taken place in a letter by Thomas Becket, who also was the dedicatee of John of Salisbury's *Policraticus*.

The *Decretum* passages examined above underline the difference between the Latin and the French letter-writers in their use of quotations. In Latin, the quotations are left unquestioned and untouched, while the writer of the French letter analyses the passages before deciding how to use them, whether by simply reproducing them or rather by working their contents into his own text.

This study on their common literary loans, whatever the source, suggests that the Latin and French writers had (received or agreed upon ?) some topics and quotations, to be freely used in their respective letters. – Referring to *iurat(ur)us* (*supra*), I think that some material was recorded in writing ; and referring to the presence of *Suëf se chastie...*, the French proverb quoted *uerbatim* in the French letter and translated in the Latin letter (*supra*), I add that the common material could at times have been French.

That the two letter-writers worked roughly at the same time and in contact with each other, seems to be a necessary condition for the parallelism of the *Decretum* quotations in the letters (*supra*), with the French letter using the French *Decretum* text where the official Latin letter mirrors the same passage from the Latin *Decretum* and neither of them indicating, by numbers or *incipits*, in what *Decretum* unit (*Distinctio* or *Causa* and *Questio*) the passage is found.

WHO WROTE THE LETTERS?

The Latin letters were the official missives, and they give the time and the place for this letter-writing activity : the year is 1166, the place, Thomas Becket's exiled court in Pontigny, that he left for Sens in November of the same year.²⁸

Who are the writers ? The official Latin letters have been sent in Thomas Becket's name but, although he can have outlined them, it is unlikely that he finalized them, as he had a secretarial staff. As there have been parallel letter drafts (Duggan 2000 : xxiii), Duggan has good grounds to believe that « some at least of the more important statements of Becket's position were corporate compositions, written and re-written by the inner ring of exiles around the archbishop » (2000 :xxiv).

Thomas Becket's irregular education was brought up already by his medieval biographers, e.g. Garnier *Mes n'aveit pas lung tens les escolles hanté* (Garnier 205), and William Fitzstephen who writes that

²⁸ Walberg (1922 :274) refers to Gervais of Canterbury who gives the date eleventh of November 1166.

when he first arrived at his predecessor's archiepiscopal court, young Thomas was the least learned of the clerics.²⁹ Thomas Becket may have been quite sensitive on this point himself. When Gilbert Foliot reminds him of the modest situation from which the king took him to be his lord chancellor, Thomas Becket develops, in the letter *Mirandum*, the notion of this alleged exiguity, stating first that he, at that time, already was an archdeacon with considerable possessions, and then, that his parents had been respectable citizens of London, but, finally, he wonders *Mais vos me reprovez/ Puet cel estre, que j'ere de sens poi aurnez* (Garnier 3422–3423) '... that my mind was poorly cultivated'.³⁰ – Barlow's (1986 :133) evaluation of Thomas Becket's scholarly aptitude may, however, be too negative : « Thomas who had not had a good grounding in grammar and rhetoric and did not have the poets or the Vulgate embedded in his memory and at his fingertips, was certainly incapable of drafting

²⁹ *In curia illa archiepiscopali magni et adprime literati clerici erant... Horum respectu Thomas minus literatus erat; sed... ipse studuit moralitati et prudentiæ intendere, ut inter eos, litteris adhuc inferior, moribus conspectior et acceptior appareret: postmodum enim literatissimus fuit* in Robertson, Mat. 3,16.

³⁰ We derive here *aurnez* from ADORNATUS (litt. 'I was of poorly decorated mind'). Thomas 2002 (« que j'étais peu doué d'intelligence pour les fonctions auxquelles j'ai été appelé ») and Short 2013 (« for having being endowed with so little intelligence ») take *aorner* to be a descendant of ADORDINARE (FEW presents both words in 24,178 and b). The Latin text does not clearly support either interpretation: *de exiguitatis mee memoria notam confusionis mii obicere uoluiti* (Duggan 432); Edward Grim has...*notam confusionis uolens obicere mihi de exiguitate mea* (Robertson, Mat. 2:410) . *Memoria* means both 'memory' and 'mind' (DMLBS 6, 1760a). – Gilbert Foliot had called Thomas Becket stupid in public (Garnier 1671; William Fitzstephen in Robertson, Mat. 3:57).

anything beyond the simplest letter. And although he probably improved his Latin, both written and oral, while in exile, we cannot doubt that he was more at home in the vernacular. » Admitting, with Barlow, that Thomas Becket ‘was more at home in the vernacular’, we are nevertheless guided by his ecclesiastical career to think that he mastered Latin reasonably well. Duggan (2000 :xxv) reminds us of Archbishop Theobald’s sending young Thomas Becket to Bologna and Auxerre to improve his legal, not literary knowledge, and of John of Salisbury’s dedicating to him *Entheticus* and *Policraticus*, and of Thomas Becket’s having a considerable Latin library (that was his most precious possession, see *infra*). Garnier mentions that Theobald took Thomas Becket to Rome together with him, and later sent him there on his errands (261-262 ; John of Salisbury Mat. 2 : 303) ; he also tells about a half-a-day altercation, in Latin, in front of the pope, between William of Pavia and Thomas Becket (2356sq).³¹

Some of his medieval biographers mention Thomas Becket’s style. Following John of Salisbury (cf. Robertson, Mat. 2,308), the Becket biography of Thomas of Froidmont (Schmidt 1991: 60) tells the reader *siue literatis siue illiteratis colloquebatur, mirum in modum eruditus et eloquens apparebat, et predicatio eius tam pondere sententiarum quam puritate uerborum placens erat et efficax*. The ‘pleasing’ and ‘fruitful’ talk to the *illiterati*, at least, must have been in vernacular. In Thomas Becket’s Latin correspondence, Duggan (2000 :xxvi) finds some private letters, and it is in them, she

³¹ The irregular schooling may have caused him social difficulties, however. He must have been regarded as an outsider by the clerics around Archbishop Theobald and, without ‘classmates’, he must have felt the lack of an informal support group.

thinks « that we come closest to Becket himself ». She finds them « characterized by a directness, indeed by a bluntness, generally lacking in the elegant sophistication of John of Salisbury », but in return « they reveal an unusual directness and independence of mind. » The private letters include three short letters addressed to Louis VII. They are written in Latin, but in the same clear and simple style we find preserved in Garnier's versification of the French letters addressed to Henry II.

The style of the Latin *Expectans*, *Desiderio*, and *Mirandum* is very different from that of the private letters : their writer is likely to be found among Thomas Becket's secretarial staff (Duggan 2000 : xxiii sq). Their redundant style with the repetitions and the show of learnedness is, I think, quite similar to the style of Herbert of Bosham's *Vita Sancti Thomae* ³² (written some fifteen years after Thomas Becket's death). Herbert of Bosham was a biblical scholar, which would also explain the correct and overly numerous Bible quotations in the Latin letters. If indeed Herbert of Bosham was involved in the composition of the Latin letters, he nevertheless could hardly have been their only writer.

'More at home in the vernacular', Thomas Becket may well have written his letters to his royal friend in their common mother tongue, a Western variety of French. The French letters show a ready knowledge of the Psalms and of the Pauline letters that could be explained by the fact, recorded by Bosham, that *sacri illi duo libri, Psalterii videlicet et Epistolarum* (Robertson, Mat. 3, 379) belonged

³² Edited by J. C. ROBERTSON, Mat. 3, 155-534. London, 1877.

to Thomas Becket's favorite reading. Regarding the French texts used in the letters, the archbishop of Canterbury must have read the Anglo-Norman *Quatre Livre des Reis*. Further, the French *Decretum* was easy for Thomas Becket to use : I attribute the translation of the text to him.

FRENCH LETTERS AND THOMAS BECKET RESEARCH

To my knowledge, the French letters have not been used in Becket research.³³ After all, since they were considered to be translations only, they have not been accorded much value as historical source texts.

As I do not think that the French letters have been translated from the existing Latin ones, but rather written as their parallel texts ; and that they then survived outside the Latin manuscript tradition, I consider them worth studying.³⁴ Their superficial similarity notwithstanding, the French letters' contents differ in so many details from the preserved official Latin letters, that they add a new voice to the discussion and may even modify some results.

³³ Walberg appreciates the value of Garnier de Pont-Saint-Maxence's poem as a whole, see his chapter «Valeur historique et littéraire du poème» (1922 : C sq) where he finds that Garnier's additions or modifications are often confirmed by later Thomas Becket *Vitas* or other historical documents (CIII).

³⁴ They may be of some use in the evaluation of the Latin manuscript texts : a particular detail that some Latin manuscripts share with the French text is likely to be authentic and original, rather than a later addition or omission or correction (e.g. the absence of *non uobis hec dicimus... penitebis* in the Latin manuscripts C and D as well as in Garnier's French text, seems to suggest that the original Latin letter did not have this passage).

While it is regrettable that the French letters are accessible to us only via Garnier's verse, it has to be kept in mind that this Frenchman – an outsider in the conflict –, who promises to tell everything and avoid all lies (*N'i voil rien trespasser, ne rien n'i voil mentir* 143), can hardly have altered the core contents of the letters with his personal opinions. Further, as already mentioned, Garnier's text, in Île-de-France dialect verse, was not easily modified by his Anglo-Norman scribes.

Text related observations.

The order of *Expectans* and *Desiderio* has been discussed by Anne Duggan on the basis of Thomas Becket's Latin letters. We will do the same on the basis of the French letters.

The majority of the collections of Thomas Becket's Latin letters seems to give *Desiderio* before *Expectans*, and this is the order of the letters in Duggan's edition. –Duggan considers *Desiderio* to be the earliest (Duggan 2000: 292-299, letter nr. 74, dated by Duggan to “late May – early June 1166”) of the three, followed by *Expectans* (Duggan 2000: 328-343, letter nr. 82, “after June 1166”) and *Mirandum* (Duggan 2000: 426-441, letter nr. 96, “early July 1166”). – Duggan thinks *Expectans* was very likely written after the Vézelay sentences.

Robertson's edition gives the letters in the order *Expectans*, *Desiderio* like Garnier's verse does.

The letter sent to the king to Chinon without a formal salutation is *Desiderio*.³⁵ However, while it lacks the word *saluz* ('greetings'), the French letter's message is formally and respectfully addressed to *Sire Reis* (Garnier 3048, cf. T-L 9, 343, 26), for which the Latin letter does not have any equivalent.³⁶ The French *Desiderio* uses the formal *vous*. The *uale* formula is absent in both versions and they end abruptly with a menace of divine vengeance unless the king restores Canterbury see to its former condition and dignity :

La sainte mere iglise de Sainte Ternité, // Restablissiez... en cele dignité // Qu'el' out as anceseurs (Garnier 3166–3170) ... *Se vus ensi nel faites, saciez certainement / Que vus en sentirez le devin vengeance* (Garnier 3179)

and

Ecclesiam... Cantuariensem... in eum statum restituitis et dignitatem in quibus fuit temporibus predecessorum uestrorum, ... Alioquin, pro certo sciatis quia diuinam seueritatem et ultionem sentietis (Duggan 298).

Expectans has both *salue* and *uale* formulas, but both are developed freely to correspond to the contents of the letter. The French greeting:

³⁵ *Ces letres senz saluz enveia a Chinon / L'arcevesques al rei* (Garnier 3042), and Gilbert Foliot takes this up in the letter *Que uestro pater* sent to Thomas Becket: *didicimus...uos... in eum comminatorium emisisse, quo salutationem omittitis* (Duggan 374).

³⁶ The Latin MS C (written in Gilbert Foliot's household) that gives the names of the sender and the recipient, points out only the lack of '*salutem*': *Henrico regi Anglorum Thomas Cantuariensis... sine 'salutem'* (Duggan 2000:293, note 1).

*Al gentil Rei Engleis, conte d'Ango, Henri,/ Duc Norman, Aquitan, sun seignur et
ami/ Thomas li arcevesques, qui jadis le servil/ Mais or est suens en Deu, saluz et
ovrer si/ Qu'il guerpisse e ament tuz les mals qu'a fait ci* (Garnier 2851–2855)

announces a letter from the archbishop to the noble English king, greeted by his high feudal titles and, then, by the appellative 'his lord and friend'³⁷, and sends him a personal greeting (*supra*) consisting of *saluz* ('health' or 'greetings') juxtaposed to an infinitive formulating a wish that he might mend his ways (Short: 'greetings and may he act in such a way that he forsake and make amends for all the wrongs that he has done in his life'). – The greeting in the Latin letter, more formal, seems to be more severe as it formulates the wish calling the recipient to *uera penitentia* 'true penance':

*Domino suo et amico Henrico, Dei gratia illustri regi Anglorum, duci Normannie,
comiti Andegauorum, et duci Aquitanie, Thomas eadem gratia ecclesie
Cantuariensis humilis minister, suus olim temporaliter, nunc autem magis in
Domino, salutem at ueram cum emendatione penitentiam* (Duggan 328).

The entire letter, in French and in Latin, calls the recipient to repent and to return to God.

The end of the French letter *La grace Deu te vaille a salu partenir,/ S'en veire humilité te vols tost repentir./ Ensi aies salu ja n'en puisses partir !* (Garnier 3038–3040) makes God's grace the subject of the verb *valoir* and gives to *salu* the meaning of 'spiritual health' or 'salvation' (Thomas' translation '... Et puisses-tu, par ce repentir, recouvrer une telle santé morale que tu ne la perdes

³⁷ This, to our mind important detail – a 'title' outside the protocole, has been omitted in Thomas's translation.

plus !'). The end of the Latin letter conveys the same worried greetings.

The French *Expectans* uses the familiar second person singular. In Old French the distinction informal/formal is not clear in the use of *tu/vous*, and the singular and plural can alternate in the same reply (Buridant 2000 :§ 336³⁸). The use of *tu* to an old friend should not have been found scandalous. – In the Latin *Expectans*, it may have been more irregular : indeed most Latin manuscripts use *uos*, and the familiar *tu* is found only in C and D. – If Herbert of Bosham was right stating (Robertson, Mat. 3 : 384-5) that Thomas Becket's letters increased in severity and, if we take the use of *vos/vus* in *Desiderio* to mean that references to old friendship were forbidden, then Garnier's letter texts would suggest the order *Expectans, Desiderio*.

On the other hand, Thomas Becket says in the Latin *Expectans* that his position obliges him to send to the king severe letters, *Et ecce inde est, quod ecclesie Cantuariensis... nos cura constringit... maiestati vestre commonitorias, exhortatorias, correptorias... destinare* (Duggan 330 ; '...letters of admonition, exhortation, rebuke...'). Should not the *Desiderio* letter, threatening the king with divine vengeance, be counted among such letters and thereby be taken as preceding the *Expectans* letter ? – The French *Expectans* would not support this argument, as it lacks all qualification for the letters Thomas Becket has been sending to the king (... *t'ai fait mes*

³⁸ The phenomenon is favored by a confusion of verb forms of singular and plural (see the variants for Garnier's line 1240 in Walberg 1922), and it is very frequent in later Anglo-Norman (Löfstedt 2010).

lettres mult sovent enveier 2887) and mentions the letters in a stanza where the king is not exhorted or reprimanded.³⁹

In turn, and clearer than the Latin *Expectans*, the French *Expectans* expresses a new grievance: the king's (men's) concrete misdeeds against the Canterbury Church, and its clergy (entire text *supra*). It states repeatedly that the king had not yet been formally blamed for them: *Suffert ai tut adés, et si m'en sui teüz* (Garnier 2861; 'I have so far tolerated everything and kept quiet') and, in a passage already discussed *Jo l'ai mis en suffrance que nel fis amender* (Garnier 2875; '...I have tolerated it without having it redressed'), and in the next stanza *Car jo part as mesfaiz, quant justise n'en fis* (Garnier 2878: '... for I am myself a partner in the misdeeds since I did not condemn them'). This is only dimly presented in the Latin text. The first example *Et licet hucusque frustra sustinuerimus, taciti considerantes...* (Duggan 328) has no clear object, and later, the message *ne excessuum uestrorum... qui circa ecclesiam Dei et personas ecclesiasticas a uobis... aguntur nimius dissimulator existam* (Duggan 330) remains submerged in a mindless verbosity (*supra*).

³⁹ In Garnier's text the mention of the many letters sent by Thomas Becket to the king form the opening lines of a stanza where Thomas Becket educates the king about the relationship of the two powers, spiritual and secular: *Reis, men voil te voldreie plainement chastier/Por ço t'ai fait mes lettres mult sovent enveier./Ne plus qu'un petiz burs puet l'onur abaisier/ Del regne, plus ne deiz.../Les dreiz de saint'iglise abatre ne changier.*(Garnier 2886; Short: 'My wish, your majesty, is to make you fully mind your ways, and this is why I have been sending you so many letters. In the same way as a little township cannot bring down the honour or the whole kingdom, so you, my King, should not modify or diminish the rights of Holy Church'.) The following stanzas deal with the same general topic.

The plundering of Canterbury is not more mentioned in the *Desiderio* letter. It seems, however, to be known to everybody involved, since, at the very end of the letter (*supra*), the king is warned for God's imminent vengeance unless he restores Canterbury cathedral to its former condition and dignity.

This is one more indication in favor of the order 1. *Expectans*, 2. *Desiderio*.

The 'lacuna' in *Expectans*. Among the Latin manuscripts transmitting Thomas Becket's correspondence, C and D, the two representatives of the Foliot group differ from the others by lacking a long passage towards the end of the *Expectans* letter. Duggan suspected that "the Foliot text was falsified to produce an appearance of deliberate insult" (2000:329, note 1). As the French *Expectans* does not convey the same impression, although it has the same 'lacuna', the passage preceding the 'lacuna' in the French and Latin letters needs to be studied.

The Latin text (Duggan 340) surrounding the 'lacuna' in the manuscripts C and D is structurally similar to Garnier's lines 3021–3037:

1. In the introduction, the letter-writer states that he now has to ask God for help, as the king's men continue to ravage the Church. 2. His words to God. 3. The king is reminded of his responsibility. 4. A warning to the king. 5. A friendly and worried closing. (The passage absent in C, D, and Garnier would be placed between 4 and 5).

I present for every segment the French and Latin texts, each of them followed by my explanations. The Bible passages referred to or quoted *uerbatim* will be identified.

1.

In the introduction the French letter-writer explains his intentions :

E se tu ne me vols oïr ne heschalcier

And if you do not want to hear me or listen to me

Qui devant le cors Deu soil Deu pur tei preier

who am used to pray for you before the Eucharist,

Jo prierai a Deu qu'il se hast de vengier

I will pray to God that He make haste to take vengeance

Les mals e les injurïes e le grant reprovier

for the wrongs and the hurt and the gross rebuke

Que tu e li tuen funt, e nel volez laissier.

that you and yours inflict and will not stop inflicting.

Certes, je crierai al Seignur de vertuz : (Garnier 3021– 3026)

Certainly I will cry to the Lord of heavenly hosts :

Seignur de vertuz (Garnier 3021 'Lord of heavenly hosts', T-L 11, 342,43) translates *Dominus uirtutum*, an expression of the Septuagint version of the Psalms, whereas St. Jerome says *Dominus exercituum*⁴⁰, in Ps. 23,10, e.g. – The Septuagint version of the Psalms has been frequently used by both letter-writers in the following text.

⁴⁰ This expression is used five times in Gratian's *Decretum* ; in all cases the French translation is only '(Lord) God' (*Dameldieu/ Damledieu, D(i)ex,*) the term *exercituum* having no equivalent. Elsewhere *exercitus* is rendered by *ost* (e.g. C 23 q 5 c 49 *Sysaram ducem exercitus sui* – l.61 *Sisara le mestre de son ost*).

In the Latin letter this introductory part is shorter :

Quod si me non audieritis, qui solitus sum ante maiestatem corporis Christi in habundantia lacrimarum et gemitibus non minimis orare pro uobis (var. te CD), certe ibidem clamabo contra uos (var. te CD) et dicam : (Duggan's transl. 'But if you do not listen to me who used to pray for you before the majesty of the Body of Christ with an abundance of tears and deep sighs, there certainly will I cry out against you, and I shall say :' Duggan 340)

This text corresponds to Garnier 3021-3023 (*Jo prierai a Deu* included). The Latin text corresponding to Garnier's 3023-3026 is adapted to be added to the words addressed to God. The Latin letter has no equivalent for *Seignur de vertuz*.

2.

The letter-writer's words to God is a desperate prayer in the French text :

Venge le sanc des tuens, Deus, qui est expanduz (ref. to LXX Ps. 78,10 or Vulg. Apoc. 19,2)

'Avenge, O God, the blood shed by your own people

E lur afflictius, dunt nombres n'est oüz.

and their countless afflictions.

De tes enemis est li orguilz si creüz

so huge has become the arrogance of your enemies

Qui tei e les tuens heent (ref. to LXX Ps. 73,22), n'en puis plus estre muz'.

who hate you and your own people, that I cannot remain silent any more.'

In the Latin text, where the words to God start earlier (*supra*), the prayer is a cold demand of punishment. There are three Bible quotations (a, b, c) :

a) *Exsurge Deus, iudica causam tuam. Memor esto improperiorum tuorum, et iniuriarum que a rege Anglorum et suis Tibi et tuis fiunt tota die. Ne obliuiscaris ignominiarum ecclesie tue, quam tuo fundasti sanguine, etc...* (Duggan's transl. 'Rise up, O God, judge your cause. Remember the insults of your servants, and the wrongs which the English king and his men are committing against you and yours every day. Do not forget', etc....) ;

b) *Vindica, Domine sanguinem seruorum tuorum qui effusus est. Vindica, Domine seruorum tuorum afflictiones, quarum infinitus est numerus* (Duggan's transl. 'Avenge, O Lord, the blood of your servants which has been poured out. Avenge, O Lord, the sufferings of your servants, too many to number') ;

c) *Superbia enim eorum qui Te et tuos oderunt et persecuntur, in tantum ascendit, ut ulterius non ualeamus eos resistere* (Duggan's transl. 'For the pride of those who hate and persecute you and yours is rising so high that we are not able to endure them any longer')

a) is a slightly modified quotation of LXX 73, 22– beg. 23 : *Exsurge Deus iudica causam tuam. Memor esto improperiorum tuorum, eorum qui ab insipiente sunt tota die. Ne obliuiscaris, etc. (ab insipiente being replaced by a rege Anglorum) ; the passage quam... sanguine presents an image used also in the Desiderio letter (Garnier 3101-3102) ;*

b) slightly modified from LXX Ps. 78,10 *ultio sanguinis seruorum tuorum qui effusus est* or Vulg. Apoc. 19,2 *uindicauit sanguinem seruorum suorum (de manibus eius) ;*

c) quotation, with additions, of LXX 73, end 23, *superbia eorum qui te oderunt ascendit.*

3.

The king is reminded of his responsibility :

Reis, qui que fet l'ovraigne, de tes mains ert requisite (3031)

King, whoever does the work, it is considered to be yours

Car bien fait le damage qui le mal en atise

For the person who stirs up the wicked act is responsible for the damage.

The Latin text is very similar:

Rex, quicquid agant uestri (agunt tui CD), hec omnia de manibus uestris (tuis CDRV) requirentur: dampnum enim dedisse uidetur, qui causam dampni dedit.

The expressions *de tes mains ert requisite (3031)* as well as the Latin *de manibus uestris requirentur* may refer to *uindicauit ... de manibus eius* Vulg. Apoc. 19,2.

4.

A warning to the king, should he not cease to disturb the clergy:

Se tu ne lais ester e clers et saint'iglise

If you do not leave clergy alone and holy Church,

Deus le vengera tost ; ja ad sa verge prise (cf. LXX Ps. 44, 7-8)

God will soon avenge it ; he already took his rod :

Tens est qu'en uelté en prenge la justice (cf. LXX Ps. 9,9 ; 66,5 ; 95,10 and 13)

it is time that he judge in this matter with equity.

Car il set bien as princes lur esperit tolir (cf. LXX Ps. 75,13) (3036)

For He knows how to take away from princes their spirit (subdue princes)

E puet bien les reis batre ; nuls ne li puet fuïr.

And He can deal blows to kings ; nobody can flee from Him.

God is presented as a just ruler and judge (LXX Ps. 44, 7-8 *uirga directionis uirga regni tui ; dilexisti iustitiam et odisti iniquitatem* ; the expression *iudicare in æquitate* occurs repeatedly in the Psalms).

Like Lat. *virga*, OFr *verge* belongs to the *regalia* and also to the formal attributes of judges (T-L, 11, 259,44 ; 260,4⁴¹). ‘God is able to subdue princes and deal blows to them’ repeats what is said earlier in the letter *Expectans*; and the reader knows already that, after repentance, the princes (like King David) are given back their former glory.

Very different in tone, the Latin text warns the king of God’s rage:

a) *Ipsē reuera Filius Altissimi, nisi resipueritis, nisi cessaueritis ab infestatione ecclesiarum et clericorum, et continueritis manus a conturbatione hominum, ad gemitus compeditorum, ad uoces clamantium ad se, ueniet in uirga furoris sui* (Duggan 340 ‘Unless you come to your senses, unless you cease attacking churches and the clergy, unless you keep your hands from causing disorder among men, the Son of the Most High will come in the staff of his fury in response to the sighs of the captives and the voices crying out to him’) b) *quoniam iam tempus est iudicare aduersum uos iusticias in equitate et seueritate spiritus sui* (‘because it is already time to pass judgment against you in the equity and sternness of his spirit’) c) *Ipsē enim nouit auferre spiritum principum, et terribilis est apud reges terre* (‘Truly he knows how to take away the spirit of princes and is terrible before the kings of the earth’)

a) the expression *continere manus* is found in Vulg. 2 Reg. 24, 16 ; *gemitus compeditorum* in LXX Ps. 78,11; *ueniet in uirga furoris sui* seems to refer to Vulg. Is. 10, 5 *vae Assur, uirga furoris mei...* where God uses the expression ‘the rod of My fury’ (‘My instrument of punishment’) of Assur whose army inflicted God’s vengeance on the Israelites;

⁴¹ *Li senechaus.../ En sa main destre une verge pelee* RCambr. 189. – St. Jerome’s Psalm translation uses here *sceptrum* : Vulg. Ps. 44, 7 *sceptrum aequitatis sceptrum regni tui; dilexisti iustitiam et odisti iniquitatem*.

b) this gloomy sentence is put together using biblical expressions *iudicare iustitias* (LXX Ps. 74,3) and *iudicare in æquitate* (LXX Ps. 9,9 ; 66, 5 e.g.), adding *et seueritate spiritus sui*;

c) is a slightly modified quotation from LXX Ps. 75, 13 ...(*reddite...*) *ei qui aufert spiritus principum, terribili apud reges terræ*. Quoted *in extenso*, the passage is particularly menacing.

5.

A friendly goodbye :

La grace Deu te vaille a salu partenir,

May God's grace be strong enough to let you be saved,

S'en veire humilité te vols tost repentir :

if you wish to repent quickly in true humility

Ensi aies salu ja n'en puisses partir !

May you find a salvation so sincere that you are never able to leave it!⁴²

This worried *uale* would fit the French letter. These final lines express the hope that, after understanding his responsibilities regarding the Church, the king find a merciful judge and be safe and saved for all eternity. In the versified French *Expectans*, there does not seem to be any 'lacuna', as the end of the part 4 and the part 5 are in the same stanza and their subjects are practically indential (God and God's grace).

The *uale* is similar in the Latin letter :

⁴² For the last line, we follow Thomas and Short. Walberg saw here two phrases.

Valeat michi cara gratia uestra, si in uera humilitate et festinata penitentia conuersus fueritis ad Dominum Deum uestrum. Valeatis sic iterum et semper (Duggan 342 ; Duggan’s transl. ‘may your grace, dear to me, fare well, if you turn to the Lord your God in true humility and speedy penance. Thus may you flourish now and always’).

The end is incompatible with the menacing and insulting text preceding it, and the conciliatory addition, found in the Latin manuscripts with the exception of C and D, was indeed well motivated.

To sum it up, the French and the Latin letter-writers use the same general plan for the passage and their common reference text has been the Septuagint version of the Psalms. Structurally similar, the letters differ in details. Most differences are found in the letter-writer’s words to God (in the Latin text, end of 1, and 2) and in the warning to the king (4).

On the basis of the French letter, and marking with < > those additions that could be ascribed to some verbose member of Thomas Becket’s staff and with **bold** letters those that radically change the tone of the letter and seem to be later additions, we could

reduce the Latin text 1–2 to :

* *Quod si me non audieritis qui solitus sum ante maiestatem corporis Christi <in habundantia lacrimarum et gemitibus non minimis> orare pro uobis (te CD), certe ibidem clamabo **contra uos** (te CD) et dicam : Exsurge Deus, iudica causam tuam. Memor esto improperiorum tuorum et iniuriarum que **a rege Anglorum et suis** Tibi et tuis fiunt tota die, ne obliuiscaris <ignominiarum ecclesie tue quam tuo fundasti sanguine>. Vindica, Domine sanguinem seruorum tuorum qui effusus est <. Vindica, Domine>, seruorum tuorum afflictiones, quarum infinitus est numerus.*

Superbia enim eorum qui Te et tuos oderunt <et persecuntur>, in tantum ascendit, ut ulterius non ualeamus eos sustinere,

and the Latin text 4, to :

* *Ipsē reuera Filius Altissimi, nisi respueritis, nisi cessaueritis ab infestatione ecclesiarum et clericorum, <et continueritis manus a conturbatione hominum, ad gemitus compeditorum, ad uoces clamantium ad se,> ueniet in uirga furoris sui; quoniam iam tempus est iudicare **aduersum uos** iustitias in equitate <et seueritate spiritus sui>. Ipse enim nouit auferre spiritum principum, et terribilis est apud reges terre.*

The Latin letter-writer's misinterpretation, as I think, of 'God's rod' damaged the text: God'(s Son) is not a just and impartial judge like in the French text, but, rather irreverently, a wild spirit of vengeance; and *iudicare iustitias* and *iudicare in æquitate* are carelessly used in a context dealing with punishment without a trial. Moreover, the expression *uirga furoris sui*, when read by a cleric well versed in the Vulgate (or the *Decretum* where Vulg. Is. 10, 5 is quoted in C 23 q 5 c 49), brings to his mind Assur, allowed by God to punish the Israelites, and might even encourage rumors of Thomas Becket's conspiring with foreign powers to bring Henry II to a fall.

Still, I think that *contra uos* (or *te*), *a rege Anglorum*, and *aduersum uos* have been added afterwards, as they intentionally change Thomas Becket from a worried and severe friend (so in the French text) to a cold and cruel enemy, and create a text absolutely incompatible with the letter's final *uale* passage.

The French letters and Thomas Becket

How do these three letters of Thomas Becket fit into the picture given of him by his biographers⁴³ ? We are told that he was born in London into an Anglo-Norman burgess family and his mother, a Frenchwoman from Caen, gave the boy a good Christian upbringing. His scholarly education was interrupted early due to the family's economic difficulties. This event seems to have troubled him even later (cf. *supra*) notwithstanding his continued studies and his quick career at the service of Theobald, archbishop of Canterbury. Soon after being ordained archdeacon by Theobald, he was recommended by him to Henry II to be the king's chancellor. The king and his counselors were very young, and Theobald was worried about their future actions. Thomas Becket's duty would be to safeguard the Church against their excesses and to diminish the influence of the royal counselors (John of Salisbury, Robertson, Mat. 2:304)⁴⁴. Thomas Becket's life at the king's service was made difficult by the other members of the royal court and, privately, Thomas Becket complained about it to his closest friends and to Archbishop Theobald (ibid. 2:305)⁴⁵. Even as a lord chancellor, Thomas Becket

⁴³ We will pay special attention to the text of John of Salisbury, a close friend of Thomas Becket's who knew Thomas Becket in his two roles, as a chancellor and as an archbishop.

⁴⁴ (Theobald) *cancellarium procurabat in curia ordinari, cuius ope et opera ne sæviret in ecclesiam, impetum cohiberet, et concilii sui temperaret malitiam et reprimeret audaciam officialium.*

⁴⁵ Thomas Becket wished ... *post vitæ æternæ desiderium super omnia... ut absque infamiæ nota posset a curiæ nexibus explicari.*

had to fight *pro domini sui regis salute et honore*, and *pro necessitate ecclesiae* (2:305). He won the king's friendship most likely not only by his pleasing personality, his legal knowledge, good memory and his assiduity, but also by being an excellent military chief *del bon hauberc armez* (Garnier 353 ; also William Fitzstephen in Robertson, Mat. 3 : 33–35)⁴⁶. The king wanted Thomas Becket to become Archbishop Theobald's successor. According to John of Salisbury, this was very much against Thomas Becket's own will as he knew the difficulties inherent in that position, *Noverat enim mores regis et officialium eius improbitatem*, and could anticipate that he was to lose either the king's grace or God's grace (ibid. 2 :305-306).⁴⁷ The only other person heard to oppose Thomas Becket's election was Gilbert Foliot, who muttered that Thomas Becket had been persecuting the Church (Garnier 478–485 ; see also William of Canterbury in Mat. 1 : 9, and Edward Grim in Mat. 2 : 367), but as

⁴⁶ The latter gives concrete descriptions at least from the year 1159: Thomas Becket was a fearless and victorious conqueror *comitibus omnibus recusantibus, solus cancellarius cum sua familia, et solo Henrico de Essexia, constabulario et barone regis, remansit. Et postea tria castra munitissima, et quae inexpugnabilia videbantur, ipsemet lorica indutus et galea cum suis in manu forti cepit. Sed et Garunnan cum militari manu transiit* (William Fitzstephen in Robertson, Mat. 3 :34) ; excellent duellist on horseback, *Ipsemet, clericus cum esset, cum valente milite Franco... lancea demissa et equo admissis congressus, ipsum equo deiecit et dextrarium lucrifeci* ; perfect military chief *Et in toto regis Anglorum exercitu semper primi erant milites cancellarii... eo docente, ducente, eo hortante...* similar exploits earned him even the admiration of the French king *Virtus quippe et in hoste laudatur* (Mat. 3 :35).

⁴⁷ ... *si oblatum subiret officium, Dei gratiam amissurus esset aut regis... Itaque aliquandiu regi et aliis eum promoveri volentibus reluctatus est.*

Gilbert Foliot had been Thomas Becket's rival to the position, his opinion was not given much attention. As there was no further opposition, Thomas Becket was consecrated in the year 1162. The following year, Gilbert Foliot became bishop of London and also the king's confessor and counselor.⁴⁸ Thomas Becket's difficulties started soon after the consecration : he did have rivals and enemies at the royal court as well as in the English clergy. The formal reason for the controversy came from the coexistence of two legal systems, one ruling the secular society and the other, the Church and clergy : on the one hand, the English secular law organized by Henry II's grandfather Henri I in the early twelfth century and, on the other, the international canon law recently compiled and explained by Gratian whose student Thomas Becket had been. In Clarendon articles Henry II reclaimed the same rights over Church and clergy that his grandfather had had. Thomas Becket first agreed to the articles orally, probably persuaded by his clergy to choose this interim solution for the welfare of the Church and to win time for negotiations (*tam pro necessitate quam pro suasibilibus magnorum uirorum religionis habitum proferentium verbis deceptus*, John of Salisbury, Mat. 2 :311), but when he immediately thereafter was

⁴⁸ *Solus Gillbertus Herefordiæ qui et postea translatus est in Londoniam... quod potuit dissuasit... aspirare enim et pro se laborare credebatur* (William Fitzstephen in Robertson, Mat. 3 :36). As he had been Thomas Becket's rival to the archbishopric of Canterbury, Gilbert Foliot resented Thomas Becket being elected and used his position as confessor to guide the king away from Thomas Becket (*Qui a l'onur tandirent, quant n'i porent entrer,/Unches puis ne finerent de mei al rei mesler*, Thomas Becket's words in Garnier 3449-3450 'those who strove to the honor, but could not reach it, never stopped to create trouble between me and the king').

demanded to ratify them by affixing his seal, he refused. Thomas Becket's opposition caused him to lose the backing of his suffragan clergy and forced him, fearing for his life, to flee from England in 1164. During Thomas Becket's long exile, Gilbert Foliot was the *de facto* ruler of the English Church.

Thomas Becket's letters *Expectans*, *Desiderio*, and *Mirandum*, were written in 1166, after two years in exile. Whether in French or in Latin, they agree in presenting the writer as an unbending archbishop who fights for the autonomy of the Church in England and wants her to be ruled by the international canon law only. In many other regards, they differ depending on the recipient of the letter and also on the language used.

What does the French *Mirandum* tell about Thomas Becket's feelings towards Gilbert Foliot? In the name of England's bishops, but without giving his own, Gilbert Foliot, the bishop of London, had written to Thomas Becket a letter (*Que uestro pater*) that started by promising *subjectiun* (Garnier 3185) to the recipient and ended by informing him that an appeal to the pope was under way in order for the anonymous letter-writers to be absolved from their obedience to Thomas Becket. In Thomas Becket's answer, in both the French and the Latin texts of the letter *Mirandum*, the letter is compared to a scorpion whose face is harmless, but whose tail gives a poisonous sting. Anne Duggan points out that Thomas Becket did recognize the true author of the letter: his answer is addressed to Gilbert of London and he uses the singular « in all but the last

paragraph which addresses the whole episcopate » (2000 : 421, note 1).

In the French text, Gilbert Foliot gets an angry rebuke for trying — once again — to appeal to the pope :

Quides tu que la pape te voille maintenir/ A ço que tu ne deies a tun maistre obeïr ?/...ne t'en volt pas oïr,/ Car il deit la maistrie e le feis sustenir/ De saint' obediencia faire par tut tenir (Garnier 3356–3360 ; ‘Do you think that the pope would support you in that you should not obey your master ? He is not going to listen to you, because he has to carry the responsibility and the burden to make sure that the holy vow of obedience is fully observed’)

In Latin, the same reprimand has a condescending addition *Male est hoc sperare de eo, et in ipsum grauiter offendere* (Duggan 428 ; Duggan’s transl. ‘It is wrong to hope for this from him and at the same time gravely offend him’).

In the bishops’ anonymous letter, Gilbert Foliot blames Thomas Becket for hurting the king. In the French *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket shrugs off such vague accusations:

Des torz me blasmes mult que jo ai fait al rei:/Nul n’en nummes, ne sai delquel respundre dei (Garnier 3389-3390 ; ‘You keep reprimanding me for the wrongs I have done to the King, but you do not mention any wrong in particular, so I do not know for which I should answer’).

In Latin, he seems to be doing some soul-searching before answering that he, for the time being, is not aware of any wrongs :

De iniuriis insimulor, quasi illatis domino nostro regi. Sed quia nullam designas ex nomine, nec ego scio cui respondere debeam. Quia ergo superficietenus accusor,

superficietenus in hac parte me excuso. Hoc tamen interim accipe responsum, quia nullius mihi conscius sum, nec propterea justificatus sum (Duggan 430 ; Duggan’s transl.’ I am charged about the wrongs allegedly inflicted on our lord the king. But since you do not specify any of them by name, I do not know to what I should answer. Therefore, because I am superficially charged, I shall excuse myself superficially in this matter. Nevertheless, accept this as an answer in the meanwhile: I am aware of nothing, nor am I justified on that account’).

In the French *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket gives Gilbert Foliot a very direct reproach:

Ne me tairai de ço que tu vols empeirier/ Ma cause, e vols le rei ainsi justefier (Garnier 3461–3462 ; Short’s transl. : ‘I am not going to remain silent about your seeking to damage my cause and thereby justify the king’),

while the reproach is barely there in the Latin text where the phrases are neutral and formal and the final exclamation presents the grievance as maybe only subjective :

Illud etiam quod ad iustificandum dominum regem uideris proposuisse, iudicauit non pretereundum leuiter uel absque discussione. Et utinam a iustitia non dissentiret et nostra aduersus eum minus iusta appareret querela (Duggan 434 ; Duggan’s transl. ‘Furthermore, I think that what you seemed to propose for the king’s justification should not be put forward lightly or without discussion. If only he were not out of harmony with justice and our quarrel with him appeared less just’).

The French *Mirandum* goes so far as to depict Gilbert Foliot as a scheming coward:

Mais encore fais pis e mult greignur mesprise,
But you do even worse and much greater damage:

Qu'od cels qui mal me quierent as vers mei guerre prise,
with those who wish to harm me, you have started a war against me,
Encontre Damnedeu e encontre s'iglise,
against God and against His Church,

Mes a celé le fais e en coverte guise ;
but you do it in secret and in an underhand way.

Tu n'en as nule hunte, ariere dos l'as mise.
It does not cause you any shame : you have forgotten all shame.

Est dunc adreement de neent restorer,
Do you mean this is redressing when nothing is restored
Tut adesseement e pis e pis ovrer ?
and things are constantly made worse and worse ?

Mais le contraire vols, puet cel estre, noter,
But maybe you wish to express the opposite,
Que servir as feluns a gré, c'est amender.
that serving felons at their will, that is to make amends:

Ainceis est ses saetes de sanc juste enivrer.

rather, it is to « make one's darts drunk with innocent blood » (ref. to Vulg. Deut. 32,42).

Mais bien me puez respondre la verité provee :
But you can give me the proven truth as an answer :

Guarder vols ta cotele, pur ço n'as point d'espee.
you wish to mind your tunic ; that is why you have no sword.

N'iert owan, se tu puez, pur espee done.

And in the present situation (lit. 'this year'), it will not be exchanged to a sword, if you can avoid it.

Ne faiz cum fist saint Piere, qui dona la colee,
You do not do like Saint Peter who gave a blow with his sword
al serf al prince aveit l'une oreille coupee.
and cut off one of the ears of the prince's servant (Garnier 3476–3490).

The recipient is said to have joined forces with Thomas Becket's enemies against the archbishop, but in secret and under cover,

without any shame, serving the felons at their will. If reprimanded, he would refer to his priestly garments as the obvious reason why he does not carry a sword. Then comes Thomas Becket's commentary : 'And in the present situation, you would not like to exchange your priestly garments against a sword, because, unlike Saint Peter, you are not fighting for your master'.

The French text's mentioning Gilbert Foliot's covert⁴⁹ actions against his master seems to be supported by the negative comparison of Gilbert Foliot to Saint Peter who showed manly valor by openly fighting for his Master⁵⁰.

The Latin text differs not only for the non-correspondence of *in coverte guise* (Garnier's 3479) and *non in occulto* ; even the reference to Saint Peter is missing :

⁴⁹ Walberg thought that the line 3479 *Mes a celé le fais e en coverte guise* was wrongly transmitted and that the lines 3479-3480 produced a *contresens* ; Thomas 2002 corrects the line 3479 to read *Mais a celé nel fais <n>e en coverte guise*, his commentary giving *Mais* the signification 'et', and his translation rendering the passage '...pas en cachette ne de manière déguisée', correction accepted in Short's translation « You do not do so secretly or in an underhand way ». Indeed, as Thomas 2002, comm. ad 3479, says, his emendated text « rejoint le latin : *et hoc non in occulto* ». If we think that clandestine scheming is (at least) as shameful as open opposition, we do not see any *contresens* in the sequence 3479-3980 as given in Garnier's text.

⁵⁰ This is what Thomas Becket expected, in vain, from all clergy : *State mecum uiriliter in proelio, apprehendite arma et scutum, et exurgite mihi in adiutorium* (from the letter *Fraternitatis*, preserved only in Latin, Duggan 392; Duggan's translation "Stand manfully with me in the fight, take up weapons and shield and rise up to my aid").

... (*quod deterius est*) *cum persecutoribus meis, et in me, Dei et ecclesie ipsius, et hoc non in occulto, stare non erubescis. Estne hoc satisfacere, perpetrata mala non corrigere, et malis deteriora de die in diem adicere? Sed fortassis illud in contrarium intelligis, ut sit satisfacere uoluntati impiorum deseruire, secundum illud 'Inebriabo sagittas meas sanguine'. Sed dicis mihi, 'Pater mi, de quibus me calumniaris, absoluam me paucis. Tunice mee timeo.'* Verum est fili mi, et nimis uerum respondes, et ideo gladium non habes (Duggan 434–436 Duggan's transl. 'but, what is much worse, you do not blush to stand with my persecutors against me, against God and his Church and this not in secret...').

In this way, the Latin text (that quotes Vulg. Deut. 32.42 *Inebriabo*, etc., correctly) may soften the tirade, but on the other hand the text lacks logic: a priest minding his garments does not stand openly (*hoc non in occulto*)⁵¹ together with knights who do the dirty work and shoot the blood-thirsty arrows.

To sum it up, the Latin letter *Mirandum*, directed to Gilbert Foliot and the English clergy, presents Thomas Becket as more controlled even when reprimanding his disobedient subordinates; a French-writing Thomas Becket is very direct – maybe overly direct – in his reprimands, showing even his disdain. The French *Mirandum* reminds us that Thomas Becket had been a military chief, used to giving orders and being obeyed, rather than a negotiating diplomat. It also makes us think that Thomas Becket's life with his learned, ceremonious, sophisticated, but cowardly and dishonest « brothers in Christ » must have been very difficult.⁵²

⁵¹ Could this text be due to an old case of dittography?: **hoc hoc (in occulto)* mistakenly read as *hoc non*: the abbreviations of *hoc* (*h* with a slanted accent) and *non* (*n* and a horizontal line above it) are quite similar.

⁵² A monk since the age of twenty, Gilbert Foliot remained ascetic in his personal life. He was an excellent letter-writer and a good administrator, but he

Next, Thomas Becket's relationship to the king. Henry II was called a friend in *Expectans*, written using the familiar *tu*, a form of address justified by the men's long, affectionate relationship.⁵³ How is their relationship expressed in the French and Latin texts of the letters *Desiderio* and *Mirandum*? I quote two passages:

The French *Desiderio* (without a salutation formula) is presented to the king preceded by a polite greeting *Sire Reis*. The sender identifies himself as Thomas Becket by giving the three reasons that cause him to want to talk to the king:

Pur treis choses pur vus, que vus voil denuncier

For three things for your own sake that I am going to tell you

D'od vus parler eü ai mult grant desirier.

changed sides many times in his life. Thomas Becket's friends, among them John of Salisbury, talked about Gilbert Foliot using the name Achitophel (e.g. Duggan 2000: 110 and 458), that of a biblical traitor. Garnier's description of him is *Des lettres sout asez, e servi Astarot* (Garnier 2172; Astarot 'the devil'). Gilbert Foliot did call Thomas Becket 'stupid' before his exile *Fous... tuzdis fustes e estes e serrez* (Garnier 1671). Garnier says about Gilbert Foliot: *Petit e petit est venuz a repentance*, but adds that he has to mend his ways completely to avoid God's punishment (3889–3890) – One would like to know what Gilbert Foliot's relationship was to the Broc family (who did the 'dirty work').

⁵³ Thomas Becket (*1118) was fifteen years Henry II's (*1133) senior. He became archdeacon of Canterbury the same year (1154) Henry II was coronated. Henry II was raised in Anjou and spent even later much time on the continent (where his domains were considerable especially after his marriage with Eleonore of Aquitania). Thomas Becket was born in London, but to a French-speaking family. The men may have been united by their common first language (Western French).

I have had a very great desire to talk with you.

Mes sire estes, dei vos e voil vos conseillier,

You are my lord; it is my (feudal) duty to give you counsel and I want to do it,

Mes reis estes, pur ço vos dei aveir mult chier,

You are my king ; because of that I have to love you,

Mes filz estes en Deu, si vos dei chastier.

You are my son in God, and I must chastise you (Garnier 3066–3070 ; Short’s transl.: ‘There are three reasons why I have fervently wished to speak to you for your own sake, as I shall explain: you are my lord, and it is therefore my duty as well as my wish to offer you advice; you are my king, and I should therefore cherish you; you are my son in God, and so I must chastise you’).

The Latin *Desiderio* that does not have any form of greeting, gives the discussed passage as follows:

Propter vos ex tribus causis : tum quia dominus meus estis, tum quia rex meus, tum quia filius meus spiritualis. Eo quod dominus, debeo uobis et offero consilium meum et obsequium (et obsequium om. C), quodcumque debet episcopus secundum honorem Dei et sancte ecclesie domino. Eo quod rex, teneor uobis ad reuerentiam et commonitionem. Eo quod filius, officii ratione ad castigationem teneor et cohertionem (292 and 294 ; Duggan’s transl. ‘On your account, there are three reasons. First, because you are my lord, second, because you are my king, and third, because you are my spiritual son. Because you are my lord, I owe and I offer you my counsel and service, whatever a bishop owes his lord, according to the honour of God and holy Church. Because you are my king, I am bound to reverence and warn you. Because you are my son, I am bound to reprove and restrain you by reason of my office’).

In the bishops’ letter, Gilbert Foliot had reproached Thomas Becket for not keeping in mind all the good the king had done to him and for not giving him anything in return. Here are some passages from Thomas Becket’s answer in the letter *Mirandum*:

Ne les bienfaiz le rei ne t'estuet pas mustrer

You don't need to tell me all the good the king has done for me.

A testemoine en puis Deu prendre e apeler

I can ask God to be my witness

Qu'en tut le munt ne poi rien plus de lui amer :

that I could not possibly have loved anything in this world more than him :

Mes qu'il laissast les dreiz de saint'iglise ester !

If only he had left the rights of the holy Church alone (lit. 'standing') !

Altrement ne puet il seürement regner.

Otherwise (= unless he does so) he can not rule safely.

Tuz les biens qu'il m'ad fait ne purreit nuls nuncier.

Nobody could tell all the good things he has done for me.

Nis s'um les pueit tuz en cent multiplier,

Even if one would multiply all of them by one hundred,

Ne dei je la dreiture de Deu pur ço laissier

I shall not therefore relinquish God's right.

Ne tei ne voil j'en ço, ne autrui, esparnier

In this matter, I do not wish to spare you or anybody else

Ne a l'angele del ciel, s'en ço voleit pechier.

nor an angel from heaven, if he would commit this sin.

E se nuls m'araisneit de ço, tost li dirreie :

And if somebody would take me up on this, I would say to him right away :

« Fui d'ici, Satanas ; ta buche Deu reneie. »

« Go away, Satan, your mouth denies God. »

Ja Damnedeu ne place que si hors del sens seie

God forbid that I would ever be so out of my mind

Que del cors Jesu Crist marcheanz estre deie

that I should be selling Christ's body

Ne mis sire li reis seit pris en cele veie.

or that my lord the king would be taken on this path (Garnier 3426–

3440).

In the Latin *Mirandum* (Duggan 432) the letter-writer explains that he values Henry II's good will and health most highly, *Testem enim Deum inuoco, nichil sub sole me gratie ipsius et saluti preponere*, but vows to defend the autonomy of the Church notwithstanding his royal benefactor's gifts, even if they were hundredfold, *Debuine pro his omnibus, uel etiamsi centuplicarentur, ecclesie Dei libertatem exponere* ? and certainly without the least care for his own fame, that quite often differs from the truth *Quanto minus pro fame mee, que sepius a uero deuiat, conseruatione* – this last phrase without equivalent in the French version. Again, the style suffers from redundant verbosity. Here is the end :

*Absit a me ista dementia. Auertat a me Deus dementia istam, ut aliquatenus persuadear aliquibus tergiuersationibus inire commercium de Christi corpore, unde ego Iude uenditori et dominus meus Iudeis assimiletur emptoribus Christi.*⁵⁴ (Duggan's translation 'Far be that madness from me. May God drive that madness away from me, that I should be persuaded in any way by any subterfuge to make traffic with the body of Christ, in which I would become like Judas, the seller, and my lord become like the Jews, the purchasers of Christ.').

Examining the two passages we see that the French and the Latin letters do not give the same picture of Thomas Becket's relationship to the king nor of the letter-writer himself.

In the French letters he is the king's friend. The French *Desiderio* begins by some lines written by a person who cannot approach his friend freely any more (hence no salutation ?), but who nevertheless wants to give him his very best advice to save him from the

⁵⁴ In Edward Grim's text, this passage (omitting only *ista... istam*) is placed at the end of the letter where it is followed by the final greetings.

imminent peril of God's severe punishment. Intelligently, he uses all three social ties (liege lord – liege man, king – subject, archbishop – spiritual son) that still unite the two men in order to gently and clearly justify a cordial albeit very serious approach. – In the French *Mirandum* the reader learns what was important for Thomas Becket: the Church – Christ's body (cf. 1 Cor. 12, 27) – that was not his to sell, but his to take care of, whose clergy, rights, possessions and privileges he was to protect against all assaults and intrusions including those of the king; and, at the same time, his sincere affection for Henry II for whom he felt deeply responsible, whom he did not want to be led astray.

The Latin *Desiderio* passage comes from the pen of a sternly formal (three causes first mentioned, then identified, then commented upon)⁵⁵ dignitary who has no personal feelings towards the king: there is not a trace of any friendship. The honest counsel promised by a man to his liege lord in the fealty oath is regulated by a coded assertion of the limits of clerical obedience, « as much as it is fitting to a bishop... ».⁵⁶ A beloved king has become only an object (*teneor*: an imposed, not chosen object) of reverence and admonishment. Instead of some quiet chastising from a father, the son will be coerced into discipline by an authority (*officii ratione*).⁵⁷

⁵⁵ Likewise in Edward Grim's version of *Desiderio* (Robertson, Mat. 2: 420).

⁵⁶ Cf. Duggan 2004: 108. The phrase signals a bishop's opposition to the Clarendon Statutes. but the king certainly already knew Thomas Becket's position in the matter. – Compare this to the analysis of a fealty oath by bishop Fulbert in his letter (a. 1020) to a duke of Aquitania, quoted in Decr. C 22 q 5 c 18.

⁵⁷ See the detailed analysis of similar passages in the Latin letters by Duggan 2004: 105-110.

– The Latin *Mirandum* passage depicts a ceremonially correct archbishop who stands for his Church, considers the king’s grace as the most important thing under the sun and shows proper concern for the king’s health, but also for his own fame (at least enough to take the time to say that he neglects it). The highsounding Latin letter lacks clarity. ‘Christ’s body’, used in the French letters as the Pauline metaphore for ‘Church’, is interpreted by the Latin letter-writer to signify Jesus of Nazareth’s physical body. Hence the overly-concrete, but not very clear image of Henry II as the Jewish buyer of Christ’s body (the chief priests did pay Judas thirty silver coins for his betrayal of Christ). One prefers the French text’s melancholy picture of a beloved king who should not be taken down the wrong path.⁵⁸

The style of the official Latin letters *Expectans* and *Desiderio*, sent to the king in the name of Thomas Becket, presents the exiled archbishop as a moderately intelligent man who is incapable of formulating his own thoughts clearly, as he gets easily side-tracked and entangled in elaborate and pompous expressions. When understandable, his chastising sounds self-righteous and boring, sometimes impolite, even rude. The French letters have been written by an intelligent and energetic person who shows easy, free mastery of the vernacular; with or without references and quotations, he expresses his personal thoughts clearly. His chastising, whether

⁵⁸ Thomas 2002 translates “et que mon seigneur le roi soit surpris par la mort sur cette voie” – we don’t think the addition “par la mort” is necessary and we would replace “surpris” by *amené*.

friendly and gentle, or hard and menacing, shows great concern for the king.

Regarding the letter-writer's relationship to the recipients, the French letters suggest that, in the year 1166, after Clarendon and when in exile, Thomas Becket's relationship to Henry II was much easier than his relationship to the clergy of England.

And Thomas Becket, was he a traitor or a friend? The crowd had called Thomas Becket a traitor (Garnier 1916–1929) when he refused to ratify the Clarendon articles. From the exile, he still refuses to fulfill the king's wishes and he even menaces the king with God's vengeance. At the same time, he repeatedly says that he is the king's friend⁵⁹, he writes to the king, he wants to see the king, and he seems to think that the present problem (like so many before it?) could be brought to a solution by a discussion between the two men. It is clear that he does not like outsiders' interference in his relationship to the king. Thomas Becket sincerely — and it seems to me, correctly — believes that the controversy and the mistakes

⁵⁹ The French letters are in harmony with Thomas Becket's answer to his accusers before leaving England *Ne jeo ne quier al rei ne mal ne deshonor/N'a humme en tut le siecle qui plus desirt s'onur* (Garnier 1601–1602), that is echoed in the exiled archbishop's letter to Louis VII *Non est enim homo mortalıs, preter dominum meum regem Anglię, in quo magis confidamus, quam in uobis de bono et honore et subsidio* (Duggan 2000: 134). Even moments before his murder, when his future killers tell him (lies?) about the King's menacing him with imprisonment, he says *mis sires li reis est tant leals e ber* ('loyal and manly')/ *Qu'il ne volsist pas teus paroles mander* (Garnier 5302–5303). Thomas Becket dislikes Henry II's advisors, and his undisciplined underlings, never Henry II himself.

attributable to Henry II are in reality due to people around the king⁶⁰.

Clearer than the Latin *Expectans*, *Desiderio* and *Mirandum*, the French letters from the year 1166 highlight a seldom discussed fact:

Thomas Becket is a sincere Catholic, who considers it his duty to use the authority of his high ecclesiastical position to have Henry II's worldly reign blessed by God and the king's immortal soul saved for heaven, by making him respect the teachings, rights and privileges of the Church. Better than the Latin letter texts, Garnier's verse gives the impression that Thomas Becket understood very literally the examples given in the *Decretum* and in the Books of Kings of fallen and restored Old Testament kingdoms: the kings were rebuked by prophets and punished for their sins, but after contrition and penance they got back their former glory and more. Thomas Becket may well have been ready to chastise the king severely⁶¹ in order to

⁶⁰ Indeed it was not the king personally, but people around him (e.g. members of the family Broc, Randulf, cf. Garnier 1929 ; 1943, or Robert, cf. Garnier 5397 ; 5406) who caused Thomas Becket's exile and murder. – In his commentary on Garnier 5126–5140, Walberg 1922 :298 identifies the king's counselors as Roger of York, Gilbert Foliot of London and Jocelyn of Salesbury.

⁶¹ In the French *Mirandum* Thomas Becket assures Gilbert Foliot, that he prefers to punish the king rather than letting him get destroyed because of his actions; and then: *Bien sai que li reis volt chastement suffrir:/En escumengement ne volt il pas chaïr* (Garnier 3396–3397; Short : 'I quite realize that the king is willing to accept being reprimanded, but he has no desire to fall under excommunication' – or, if *voloir* marks here the future (cf. T-L 11,748, 13) '...the king will accept the rebuke...') or in Latin: *Absit autem ut tecum sentiamus dominum nostrum regem impatientem correptionis ad exterminationem apostasie lapsurum* (Duggan 2000: 430; Duggan's transl. 'God forbid, however, that we should think with you that our lord the king, impatient of correction, is about to fall into the extremes of

avoid God's vengeance (which he feared to be imminent, as he said at the end of *Desiderio*) ; he believed that this harsh treatment would bring the king back to God and let him emerge happy and victorious as a new King David⁶².

Was this a sign of a total change of heart, compared to Thomas Becket's excellent service to the king as his lord chancellor, when he may even have tolerated some damage to be caused to the Church? It should be borne in mind that Theobald chose Thomas Becket to be Henry II's chancellor in order to safeguard the Church from the young, proud and unruly prince's excesses and to restrain the influence of his wicked counselors on him. Already as a lord chancellor, Thomas Becket had to fight *pro domini sui regis salute et honore*, and *pro necessitate ecclesiae*. Faithful to the wish of his late predecessor, Thomas Becket, even when in exile, repeatedly wants Henry II to respect the Church's privileges and to send away his wicked counselors, but *Ire e malveis conseil unt le rei deceü* (Garnier 1696 ; 'anger and bad counsel deceived the king').

Change of heart? While we are told that his courtly habit is changed to a clerical one (with a hair shirt underneath), that he

apostasy'). – The Pope had not granted Thomas Becket any mandate concerning the king: in his letter from April/May 1166, the Pope makes Thomas Becket aware of this restriction *Verum de persona regis speciale tibi mandatum non damus* (Duggan 2000: 272).

⁶² In *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket expresses his belief in the king's good character and Christian education: *Ço que Deus ad planté, ne larra pas perir* (Garnier 3398) or *Non enim Patris celestis plantatio eradicabitur* (Duggan 2000:430).

prays much⁶³, attends regularly the divine service, and that the Pauline letters, the Psalms and the *Decretum* become his regular reading material and also that he observed a claustral diet as much as his body could tolerate, although never for a public show⁶⁴, I do not think there was much change in his feelings towards the king or in his endeavour to fulfill Theobald's wishes. In the letter *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket reprimands Gilbert Foliot for not caring for the king's spiritual well-being, in Latin :

[...] *providere debueras, cui te fauere dicis, domino nostro regi; qui, quamdiu sic aget in nos uel in ecclesiam Christi, nec ad bella procedere uel in pace degere sine anime sue periculo poterit* (Duggan 428-430 ; Duggan's transl. 'you who say that you support him, should have made provision for our lord the king, since he can neither go to war nor remain at peace without danger for his soul, as long as he acts thus against us and Christ's Church');

and in French :

De ço qu'obediensce as a tun dit pramise/ Nostre seignur le rei, n'as nule garde prise/ E tant cum il voldra vers nus ensi errer/ E envers saint'iglise, que devreit honurer,/ Ne purra en bataille seürement aller,/ Ne en pes ne en guerre ne vivre ne ester,/ Que le peril de s'aneme ne puisse mult duter (Garnier 3374-3380).

Gilbert Foliot did not warn the king of any divine vengeance for his actions against the Church, although he — the king's confessor

⁶³ Thomas Becket often goes into his study closing the door (Garnier 3905) and the biographers think that this time is used for prayer and *contemplatiun* (3910). We suspect that some of it was dedicated to the translation of the *Decretum* (a translation adjusted to lay people's reading and possibly destined to Henry II, cf. Löfstedt 2001: 41).

⁶⁴ *in ueste pretiosa spiritu pauper, in facie læta corde contritus, in mensa lauta penuriam eligens* (John of Salisbury in Robertson, Mat. 2, 308)

— had said that he ‘supports’ the king. Here the Latin text uses *fauere* ‘show favor’, but the French has the phrase *pramettre obediēce*. As *obediēce* here is promised to a king, the word does not seem to have its normal religious meaning, but rather signifies *obeissance* ‘service of a vassal’ (FEW 7, 277ab). I take from this that when Thomas Becket repeatedly (Garnier 2888–2890 ; 2922 ; 3156–3166 and elsewhere) tells the king to respect the autonomy of the Church, even at times menacing him with punishment, he is only serving the king. Indeed, among the six things a vassal has to pay attention to in his fealty oath (*incolume, tutum, honestum, utile, facile, possibile* Decr. C 22 q 5 c 18), one finds the sovereign’s safety. The king could not be safe in any situation, if his actions had called God’s vengeance upon him. Earlier, Thomas Becket protected his king in the capacity of a lord chancellor and military chief ; this time, he is the archbishop responsible for his king’s safety in this life and salvation in the next.

THOMAS BECKET’S FRENCH AND LATIN LETTERS : MORE PROBLEMS REMAIN

While the simple and sincere French letters may have had some chances to revive the old friendship and to reconcile the archbishop with his king, the Latin letters would have irritated any reader and they infuriated Henry II (Duggan 2004 :105-106).

Indeed, how were the French letters used ? Did they only remain among the letter-writer’s personal documents ? Were they used by the messenger who carried the official letters to their recipient and

presented him with their contents in vernacular?⁶⁵ The French *Desiderio* starts with *Sire Reis*, as if giving the messenger his first polite words. But did the French letters ever reach the persons they were intended for?

If not, was Thomas Becket a victim of a protocol using Latin? Was he a victim, first, of his secretaries' epistolary style and even of their personal feelings?⁶⁶ I think that the French letters do convey Thomas Becket's own messages to the respective recipients, but to what extent did he exercise any control over the writing of the official Latin letters in accordance with his own wishes? Unfortunately, we do not know what these Latin letters looked like when they left the exiled court in 1166, as they have been preserved only in later copies. As shown above, the overall impressions (of

⁶⁵ Duggan describes the presentation of the letters to the recipient: "The real message... was 'in the mouth of the bearer'... a mediator, unconnected with the dispute between king and archbishop. His pleas, spoken in the French vernacular, were likely to have been on the level of personal appeal to the king's justice and mercy, and presented with befitting monastic humility. That part of the message has not been recorded..."(Duggan 2004 :107).

⁶⁶ The attitude towards Henry II revealed in the Latin text of *Expectans* and *Desiderio* could be that of Herbert of Bosham, whose authorship could also be suggested by the style of the letters. P-G. Schmidt describes Herbert of Bosham's Thomas Becket *Vita* (1989:132): "Ihre unbestreitbar wichtigen, aus engster persönlicher Nähe gewonnenen Informationen sind unter einem Wust und Schwulst von Reflexionen, Meditationen und Repetitionen versteckt", adding that Herbert of Bosham admitted himself "sepius idem uoluo et reuoluo". Herbert of Bosham is characterized by Schmidt (ibid.) as irritable, aggressive and very rigoristic. "Dem Erzbischof war er ein Ratgeber gewesen, der zur Verschärfung der Konflikte beitrug; nach dessen Ermordung hielt er direkt und ohne diplomatische Verbrämung König Heinrich II. ... die Schuld an der Tat vor".

Thomas Becket, of his relationship to the recipients), conveyed by those copies differ greatly from the impression given by the French letters.

Comparing the two versions of an *Expectans* passage where Thomas Becket makes the king aware of the damage his men were causing in Canterbury, we found that the text preserved in all Latin manuscripts was very unclear due to redundancies. The most disturbing secondary features, however, were easy to remove without modifying the underlying text (*supra*). This discovery seemed to imply that they had been added afterwards into that letter text : they made its sender appear stupid. – Likewise, a comparative analysis of the original text of *Expectans* preceding the final *uale*, detected in all Latin manuscripts the addition of some aggressively hostile expressions (*contra vos*), which presented the letter's sender, Thomas Becket, as the king's enemy and transformed the Latin version of *Expectans* into a cold, hateful and cruel missive with which the letter's friendly *uale* phrase was in disaccord (*supra*).

These observations suggest that Thomas Becket became also a victim of some person(s) (close to Henry II ?), who had gained immediate access to the letters addressed to the king and who, wishing to aggravate the controversy, added superfluous, asinine or insulting, expressions into the text before it was copied, making the king's former friend present himself in the official records as both ridiculous and vicious — even unfit for his high ecclesiastical position.

It would be easy to find people in the high clergy of England who did not have any interest in the archbishop's possible return to England and in the revival of his close friendship with the king. One

such person who may even have had easy access to Thomas Becket's correspondence with the king, is the king's confessor and counselor, Gilbert Foliot, Thomas Becket's rival and enemy and, during Thomas Becket's exile, the *de facto* leader of England's Church, an excellent letter-writer himself who certainly knew that « le style est l'homme même » before Buffon formulated the adage. He could be suspected to be behind some alterations visible in the manuscripts C and D that “draw on materials found in Foliot's own household” (Duggan 2000:ci), but it is striking that some passages that to my mind are secondary ‘alterations’ in the Latin text, are found even in manuscripts deriving from the alpha and beta collections (e.g. in Duggan's basis manuscript). These two early collections themselves, alpha and beta, « made from records kept by Becket's household in exile » (Duggan 2000 :lxx) have been lost.⁶⁷

At least, there must have been several occasions for Thomas Becket's enemies to ‘edit’ the exiled archbishop's letters as there is a considerable time span between the original lost letters from the year 1166 and their first preserved copies. *Expectans*, I think, could have been ‘edited’ twice : first, by adding among other things the hostile expressions (like *contra uos*, resulting in the text of all Latin manuscripts including C and D) and in ‘second edition’ adding the conciliatory passage (resulting in the text of all Latin manuscripts

⁶⁷ We know that, immediately following the murder in Canterbury, the episcopal residence was ransacked and thoroughly burglarized by Robert del Broc and his men (Garnier 5661-5680). Not satisfied with gold and silver, the knights even took Thomas Becket's books and all his writings (*Pris i furent si livre et trestuit si escrit*, Garnier 5665). We do not know whether among the destroyed or confiscated items were any copies of the archbishop's letters sent from the exile.

except C and D). The ‘second edition’ could be dated to a time after Thomas Becket’s death (1170) or after his canonization (1173), as it takes away some of the negative feelings conveyed by the Latin letter. (The sainted archbishop’s public image had changed and his official letters should accordingly reflect the change.)

It should be noted that Edward Grim who used *Desiderio* and *Mirandum* (ca. 1172), does not have *Expectans*. Was this his personal choice or was that letter not being shown at the moment?

Indeed, there have been intentional alterations of an – already sent – document as it was copied for record keeping. One is found in *Que vestro pater*, Gilbert Foliot’s own letter, although sent anonymously in the name of English bishops (Thomas Becket answers to Gilbert Foliot in *Mirandum*). In the preserved *Que uestro*, the bishops announce their appeal to the pope by *remedium uobis appellationis opponimus* (Duggan 380; Duggan’s transl. ‘we oppose against you the remedy of appeal’). The Latin *Mirandum* takes up the announcement by *Et illud uide quo sensu dixeris, ‘ad appellationis remedium confugimus’* (Duggan 428), where a direct quotation seems to refer to the actual announcement, although wording it differently. Noticing the lack of correspondence, Duggan thinks that “it is more likely that this letter (i.e. *Mirandum*) responds to a lost letter from Gilbert himself” (2000:426, note 1; 429, note 8).

I think that *Que uestro* may have had two appeal announcements, one that was used in the original letter (and that still is quoted in *Mirandum*), and another, a later corrected variant (found in the official copies of *Que uestro*).

In the text preceding the announcement of the appeal, the writer of *Que uestro* describes members of the English Church as sheep looking for safety that they do not get from their archbishop:

(ne consilio precipiti mactare pergatis et perdere sed commissis ouibus ut uitam... ut securitatem habeant... studeatis, Duggan 380; ‘do not continue by too hasty a judgment to ruin and destroy, but... endeavour to make provision that the sheep committed to your charge may have life... and security’);

he adds that the English bishops complain about a colleague’s being excommunicated by Thomas Becket; and feel the danger that the king or even some of themselves could be Thomas Becket’s next victims — after which the phrase *ad appellationis remedium confugimus* would most naturally invite a very concrete interpretation, ‘we flee to the aid of an appeal’. And it is this very variant of appeal announcement that Garnier found in the *Que vestro* text he had access to and whose translation⁶⁸ he versifies:

Apeluns pur remedie e refui de l’esfrei (Garnier 3315; ‘we appeal for remedy and refuge from the turmoil’).

In *Mirandum*, Thomas Becket seems to play with the ‘flight’ of his disorderly flock:

Quid... est primo recognoscere debitam nobis subiectionem, et subiectioni coherentem obedienciam promittere, demum, ne obedire debeas, ad appellationem conuolare? (Duggan 428; Duggan’s transl. ‘For what... is it, first to recognize the

⁶⁸ Garnier’s *Que uestro* is a versification of a reasonably exact translation (by Garnier?) of the Latin letter.

subjection due to us and to promise the obedience which is linked to subordination, then to fly to an appeal so that you need not obey?’).

Subsequently, Gilbert Foliot may have preferred to correct *Que uestro*’s wording for the official copy of the letter. The new announcement of appeal does not allow the amusing concrete interpretation: in *remedium uobis appellationis opponimus* the word *remedium* means (not ‘help’, ‘medication’ or ‘relief’), but ‘legal instrument’ (*remedium appellationis* ‘writ of appeal’), as it sometimes does already in the Roman law (cf. CIC C 2, 9, 3). After the correction, the ‘edited’ letter shows the *grauitas* of the learned bishops.

We already mentioned that the French letters were close to Latin private letters. At least *Desiderio* is a warning message meant for the king alone (and, I think, meant to be given to him privately by the messenger whose *Sire reis* would greet the king) : from its beginning (without the formal salutation) to its very end (without a formal *uale* formula) it conveys the writer’s feeling of alarm, of imminent danger.⁶⁹ It seems to be sent for the recipient’s immediate personal attention, like a *dépêche* or a telegram of later times. It was hardly

⁶⁹ Cf. *Audiat itaque dominus meus, si placet, consilium fidelis sui, commonitionem episcopi sui, et castigationem patris sui; nec cum scismaticis aliquam de cetero habeat communionem uel familiaritatem, nec cum eis aliquo modo contrahat* (Duggan 296; Duggan’s transl. ‘Therefore, if it please my lord,... let him not in the future have any friendship or communion with schismatics, or make any agreement with them in any way’) and also ... *od les puruers n’aiez mais nul cumunement* (Garnier 3150). The letter was written at a time when Henry II was dealing with Frederic I Barbarossa, a staunch supporter of the antipope.

meant to be read aloud in the middle of Henry II's council meeting at Chinon. Who decided how the letters were to be presented?

GARNIER

I have taken Garnier to be a faithful versifier of Thomas Becket's French letters. He does not seem to have added any unauthentic material into the letter texts. Since he was a Frenchman, Garnier did not know the letters' English recipients: consequently, when versifying the letters, he was not tempted to color them with his own personal feelings. His long verse lines, twelve-syllable alexandrines, could allow him to remain very true to his original. On the other hand, because they were written in alexandrines and in five-line stanzas in the Île-de-France dialect and 'hidden' in a hagiography, the letters were reasonably safe against alterations by people whose French was Anglo-Norman and, very often, only their second language.

What do we know of Garnier? He was born in Pont-Sainte-Maxence in Sellentois, Northern Île-de-France (*Guernes li clers, del Punt Sainte Mesence nez Garnier 5877*), and he may also have begun his clerical life there, since he calls himself *Guernes li clers del Punt* (Garnier 6156). We do not know where he spent his early years, except that he was a cleric. He was proud of being born in (Île-de)France and, therefore, of being able to write good French.

Garnier did not know Thomas Becket as the lord chancellor, although he had seen Thomas Becket attack the French as Henry II's military commander *E jeol vi sur Franceis plusurs feiz chevalchier*

(359). He does not disclose how he got inspired to write a hagiographic poem about Thomas Becket. At the very end of his work, Garnier gives the time when he began the work *L'an secund que li sainz fu en s'iglise ocis/ Comenchai cest romanz* (6166–6167), and in the prologue (144) he mentions that he worked on his hagiographic poem for nearly four years (finishing it the year 1174?, the year after the canonization), correcting his text and seeking the truth (*N'i voil rien trespasser, ne rien n'i voil mentir* 143). His first drafts, still quite imperfect, had been stolen⁷⁰. When first beginning his work, Garnier says (146), he had relied on hearsay, but later he traveled to Britain to find the truth from persons who had known the saint. Without identifying any predecessors who wrote in vernacular about the martyr, Garnier adds that there were many lies in earlier French stories about Becket, be they written by clerics or laymen, monks or abbots: *Tut cil autre romanz* ('works written in Romance vernacular' T-L 8,1441,8) *ke unt fait del martyr/ Clerc u lai, muine u dame, mult les oi mentir* (161–162). We do not know of any such early vernacular narratives of Becket.

It is unknown when Garnier crossed the Channel: we find him (Walberg, *Vie*, Appendix) as a guest in Barking welcomed by the nuns and Abbess Marie, Thomas Becket's sister, who became an abbess in 1173; and he has used intelligently the Latin Becket *Vitas* by Edward Grim (written ca. 1172) and William of Canterbury (who wrote between June 1172 and December 1174), whom he quite likely

⁷⁰ See the text presented by I. Short "Vie de Saint Thomas Becket" in *Medium Ævum* 46 (1977): 20-34. This text fragment is translated in Short 2013, 173 sq. It does not concern us here, as it does not contain any letter text.

even met.⁷¹ As observed in earlier research (cf. Walberg 1915:27, note 2; 28, note 1, and commentaries passim; Walberg 1922:LXIV sq; Thomas 2002, vol. 2: 381), Garnier may do much more than just repeat his sources :

When recounting that Thomas Becket was wrongly suspected of having an affair with a former lady-friend of Henry II, Garnier (300–333) adds to his story the lady’s name as well as the name of the inn-keeper who spied on the two: his obvious source, William of Canterbury (Robertson, Mat. 1, 6), does not have the names.

Like William of Canterbury (Robertson, Mat. 1:19–23), Garnier reports all of the Clarendon articles. Garnier (2396–2490) adds, after each article, his own commentary (Walberg 1922: LXXXII “commentaire original”). The article text is given in indirect speech, the commentary in direct speech, e.g. (article fifteen):

Plait qui fuissent de dete, u par fei u senz fei/ Tel plait deüssent estre tuit en la curt le rei./ - De crimene en laie curt par dreit plaidier ne dei... (Garnier 2536–2538 ; Short 2013 : ‘Pleas related to debt, whether entered into under oath or not⁷² , should all be heard in the king’s court. — Legally I am not required to plead in a lay court...’).

Garnier’s personal commentary may have required a field reporter’s work. According to article twelve, the income of all vacant sees, abbeys, etc. should come to the crown until a new bishop,

⁷¹ See Duggan (1980 :203 sq) *supra*. The dates we give come from Schmidt 1989 :134. Neither Edward Grim nor William of Canterbury has versions of *Expectans*; see our tables for Edward Grim’s texts for *Desiderio* and *Mirandum*.

⁷² The Latin expression is *fide interposita...uel absque interpositione fidei*, Thomas 2002: comm. 153; William of Canterbury (Robertson, Mat. 1,23).

abbot, etc. is installed. Garnier had several occasions to observe the consequences of this article and he writes:

*Jo ving en pluisurs lius que li reis out saisiz:/N'i esteit nuls des hostes ne povres
recuilliz;/Jo fui defors la porte del portier escundiz;/Carité n'i fu pas, c'entendi a ses
diz... (2491–2494; 'I went to many places that the king had seized: no visitors or
poor people were received there. I was told, by the gate-keeper, to go away from
the gate. There was no charity, that I understood from his words...').*

On the other hand, after the article sixteen stating that a serf's son cannot be ordained without the lord's approval

*Fiz a vilain ne fust en nul liu ordenez/ Senz l'asens sun seignur, de qui terre il fust
nez (Garnier 2541-2542),*

Garnier's commentary

*E Deus a sun servise nus ad tuz apelez!/ Mielz valt fiz a vilain qui est prouz e senez/
Que ne fait gentilz hum failliz e deboutez (Garnier 2543–2545)*

raises a question : while it reflects a recommendable personal opinion, it makes us wonder how well Garnier knew canon law, as Decr. D 54 gives a rather strong support for article sixteen.⁷³

⁷³ A similar error regarding the canon law occurs in Garnier's text of *Que vestro*. Gilbert Foliot is recorded saying to Becket about Henry II *Quid enim, si uestra, quod absit, exacerbatione et opera, dominus noster quem largiente Domino populi secuntur et regna, a domino papa recesserit* (Duggan 2000: 376), but the text is presented by Garnier *Que dirrez se li reis, qui li regnes apent, E qui a desuz li e les clers e la gent./Se part de l'apostoile par vostre anguissement?* (Garnier 3266–3268). In the official Latin text Foliot does not say that Henry II has even the

When a monk from Christ Church tells the former chancellor and the newly-consecrated archbishop that he should change his worldly dress, Thomas Becket's first reaction is, according to Garnier, laughter or a smile:

Quant l'arceveske l'ot, un ris li ad jeté/Partie li mustra de ceo qu'out en pensé (546-547; 'Having heard this, the archbishop looked at him with a smile; and told him a part of what he had been thinking').

According to the Latin tradition that goes back to Edward Grim and is continued by Thomas of Froimont, Thomas Becket's reaction was quite the opposite: he shed bitter tears (*Quod audiens uir uenerabilis lacrimatus est amarissime ...* Schmidt 1991:36). To our mind, Garnier's text could be closer to the historical truth: a chancellor does not cry in public; the tears belong to a hagiography.

Edward Grim does not explain how Thomas Becket left the office of chancellor after being elected to archbishop (1162) on the king's instigation; the king himself was in Normandy at the time. The formal leaving of the office demanded by the wise bishop of Winchester (*L'eveske de Wincestre, ki mult sot de raisun*, Garnier 514) is an important detail, since members of a lay court (*curiae nexibus obligati*, Decr. D 51 c 5) could not become bishops. Garnier reports this event (505–529) and Walberg (1915: 27, note 2) finds

clergy in his command. Garnier's blunder (he was not a canonist) or Gilbert Foliot's 'editorial' correction?

supporting evidence from William of Canterbury (cf. Robertson, Mat. 1: 8)⁷⁴ for Garnier's lines:

Les justices le rei, ki il ot comandé / Ke quanqu'il en fereient par li ert cumfermé / E sis fils ensement l'en unt quite clamé / D'acuntes, de tut el, e al clergié livré (Garnier 526–529 ; 'the king's justices to whom he [Henry II] had given such a mandate that everything they would do would be ratified by him, and also his son [the future Young King]⁷⁵ Henry declared him [Thomas Becket] free from the accounts and from everything else [i.e. discharged him from all accountability, making him immune from any future claims] and handed him over to the clergy').

These lines let the reader understand how wrong Henry II's actions were a couple of years later when he sent his knights to the archbishop:

Or volt que il li rende ses acuntes pleniens / De quanqu'ot en baillie, quant fu ses chanceliers (Garnier 1837–1838 'now he [the king] wants that Thomas Becket give full account of everything he was in charge of while he was the king's chancellor').

Describing the court-ordered public apology of Philippe de Broï, a canon of Bedford of noble birth, who was to try to make peace with a knight he had offended, Garnier reports that Philippe, disrobed,

⁷⁴ Cf. Robertson, Mat. 1:8 *Cautum est autem ut novo regi, filio regis, ... electio præsentaretur... A quo a publicis negotiis absolutus, post modicum... in Cantuariensi ecclesia consecratus est*. Walberg (1915:27, note 2) refers also to Ralph de Diceto's work (I, 307).

⁷⁵ Henry (1155–1183) was seven years old.

had to offer his arms to the knight in the presence of the (knight's) family⁷⁶ and then,

A la lei del país desus li jurereit: /De tel mesfet de lui tel amende prendreit (Garnier 814–815; ‘...that he would be willing to accept (from the knight) for the same offense the sort of compensation he now was offering’).

I have said earlier (Löfstedt 1991:8) that the *lei del país* ‘law of the land’ seems to be *Leis Willelme*, 10, 2 (Liebermann, 1, 1903: 500)

Puis a l'acordement, si lui metera avant honurs e jurra, que, s'il lui oust fai<t> ceo qu'il lui ad fet, e se sun quor purportast e sun conseil lui dunast, prendreit de lui ceo que offert ad a lui ‘then at the reconciliation, may he [A] put [valuable] gifts [‘marks of esteem’]⁷⁷ in front of him [B] and swear that if he [B] had done to him [A] the same thing he [A] had done to him [B, i.e. if the roles were reversed], and if his heart would be willing and his (family) counsel would allow it, he would take what the other offered to him’

(following the *Leis Willelme* paragraph, the offended party would have made peace with the offender by taking the gifts offered by the offender).

⁷⁶ *Veant ses amis* ‘so that his friends see it’ ; in old laws, the *amis* are often family members (T-L 1, 351,11), people whom the party trusts and who have the authority to counsel him/her. Liebermann (2, 1906, s.v. *amici*), gives a reference to Edward the Confessors Laws, 36.5 retr., where he translates *amici* by ‘Blutsfreunde, Verwandte’ and compares its use to that of Anglo-Saxon *freond*.

⁷⁷ *Leges Henrici Primi* 36 (Liebermann 1, 1903: 566) present in more detail the same procedure of reconciliation after a show of disrespect, outrage. We quote: *armis hoc et honoribus... emendetur* (36.1; the words *armis* and *honoribus* seem to be nearly synonymous) ; and *Quod si iuramentum pacationis exigitur, iuret... quod si ille sic esset pro huiusmodi forisfacto, hoc reciperet uel hoc modo dimitteret* (36.1 d). – See also the chapter “Ehrenbezeugung” in Liebermann 2: 373b.

Garnier may refer to the same old reconciliation rite later when he describes Thomas Becket's ending his long exile in France and saying to a friend, who warned him of the perils ahead that, after leaving his Church alone for seven years, he wants to go home to Canterbury or, should he die before reaching it, to be carried to his church, adding

E si faites mes livres ensemble od mei porter;/ Se jo ainc nes servi dunt se puissent loer,/Pur ma possessiun m'i voillent honorer./N'um ne puet en la fin a l'umme plus doner/Que ço qu'il plus desire s'um li volt graanter (4676–4680 'And have my books be carried with me; if I earlier did not serve them in a way they approve of, may they want to honor me because of my possessions. After all, a man cannot give to a[nother] man more than what he most wants to have himself, if the [other] man would accept it').

We see here Thomas Becket taking the role of the offender who seeks reconciliation by offering to the offended party (Canterbury and the Church of England) his dearest and most prized possessions (not arms, but books) and hoping that the gift is accepted. Short's translation of the end shows a different interpretation (139): 'when it comes to the final reckoning, no one can give a better present to anyone than to be willing to grant what he himself treasures the most': he attaches *s'um li volt graanter* to the giver. In his translation: 'Et faites-y porter mes livres avec moi : si, auparavant, je n'ai rendu à mes ouailles aucun service dont elles aient à se féliciter, qu'elles vueillent bien m'y honorer pour cette donation. À un homme sur la fin de sa vie, on ne saurait faire de plus beau présent que de lui accorder, si on le peut, ce qu'il désire le plus', Thomas

takes *en la fin*⁷⁸ to be a reference to the end of Thomas Becket's life and, the entire stanza, to Thomas Becket's last will. He may be (mis)guided by William of Canterbury's slightly different text (quoted Thomas 2002: comm. 256, Robertson, Mat.1:86-87) :

nihil est enim quod magis hominibus debeatur quam ut suprema voluntas, postquam aliud velle non possunt, adimpleatur ('there is nothing more one should do to others than to fulfill their last wish, after which they cannot wish for anything').

Edward Grim was a cleric from Cambridge, who had recently come to Canterbury at the time of Thomas Becket's death. He was severely wounded in the cathedral while trying to protect the saint. William of Canterbury, a Benedictine monk from Christ Church, was ordained dean of Canterbury by Thomas Becket a few days before the murder and was then appointed to be the guardian of the tomb (Schmidt 1989: 135). In this way he became a witness and recorder of the many miracles that happened there. Garnier recalls that he often came to Thomas Becket's tomb to read his *Vie* (Garnier 6156sq); it is likely that he met William. Both authors were well suited to help Garnier's research on Thomas Becket's life in England.

However, in Garnier's 6180-verse text, the archbishop's exile starts already in verse 1950⁷⁹ and he returns to England only in the

⁷⁸ Could it not refer to the expected end of the controversy as well ? In T-L 3,1861,44 *en la fin* in interpreted as an adverb and translated 'zuletzt, endlich' ('finally').

⁷⁹ Garnier tells about Thomas Becket as the archbishop from verse 395 on; then, from verse 735 on, about the conflict between the king and the archbishop.

verse 4717. France becomes thus the background for most of the events described by Garnier. One would assume that this French-born writer had acquainted himself with the two French surroundings of the exiled archbishop, Pontigny and Sens, as well as with his former household and servants, clerics and laymen, and his library and any writings that were left behind, when Thomas Becket returned to England in haste.

Garnier is likely to have learned in France the names of the abbots Guichard (*Guischar l'abé* 2559) and Garin (*li abes Guarins* 3711), Thomas Becket's hosts in Pontigny; his Latin sources do not give them; nor do they mention that Thomas Becket's marshal William de Capes⁸⁰ was his bodyguard during one evening swim (*Iluec curreit un'ewe.../ La se baignout les seirs.../ A Willame de Capes se fist un seir guaitier* 3626–3628), and that William later also healed him from a painful infection by extracting *Dous osselez* (3634 meaning 'impacted wisdom teeth'?) from his mouth. Only Garnier seems to know the name of the archbishop's personal attendant Brun (*Brun, sun vaslet, si cum dire l'oï,/ Qui ses haires lava* 3978–3979; v. Walberg 1922 : LXXXV) and his messenger Madoc (*Madoc bailla les lettres* 4289; v. Walberg 1922 : 283). Garnier (3650–3670) reports that a lay brother in Pontigny was healed by Thomas Becket; the incident is presented as a miracle in a later anonymous *Passio* (Walberg 1922 : LXXXIII). Garnier tells about two men, *uns huem* (3841) and *Uns altres* (3846), offering each of them to provide financial support to the exiled archbishop, after Henry II made his stay with the Cistercians difficult (3841–3850) and before the French

⁸⁰ Garnier introduces this person earlier (Garnier 2046; Walberg 1922: 251).

king took the exiled court to Sens. Rather than in England, it may be in France that Garnier learned about Thomas Becket's interpretation of the failure of his first attempt to flee from England :

L'arceveske l'a puis suvent issi cunté/N'uncor ne l'aveit Deus a passer apresté,/N'il n'ot uncore pas el champ estreit esté (Garnier 1371–1374 ; 'The archbishop often told it later in this way : God had not yet prepared him to go, nor had he yet been in the narrow battle field', i.e. fenced-in duel arena)⁸¹,

or about God making the flight proper possible by using the sharp eye and quick actions of the archbishop's squire Trunchet⁸² (Garnier 1956-1965), or about the archbishop's very personal wish to have his fine library taken to England (*supra*). As the murderers, lead by Robert del Broc (Garnier 5658), made sure to plunder and destroy everything in Thomas Becket's living quarters at the Canterbury cathedral, so that *Pris i furent si livre e trestuit si escrit* (Garnier 5665 ; 'his books and all of his writings were taken'), the English biographers may have had much less material from Thomas Becket's exile time to work on than Garnier.

Examining the « Getty Gratian » (J. Paul Getty Center, 83 MQ 163 : Ludwig XIV :2 ; 1170–1180 ; a manuscript attached to Thomas

⁸¹ Edward Grim's version is much less concrete : *Sanctus uero recognovit postea et suis confessus est necdum fuisse voluntatis Dei ut tunc transfretasset, adhuc illi certamen grave reservatum, et tentationes per quas transiret ut probator appareret ; quod factum est* (Grim in Robertson, Mat. 2 :390).

⁸² Walberg (1922 :LXXVIII) mentions that Roger de Pontigny calls this person *Petrus de Mortorio*. He is not mentioned by Edward Grim or William of Canterbury, the latter telling only of the gate-keeper being occupied in some punitive action, *quendam cædens virga officii sui* (Robertson, Mat. 1: 40).

Becket's exile court) and the contemporary illuminated notes on its margins (Löfstedt 2015 : 197, n. 13), I found at C 10 q 2 c 2 *Nota illud esse guarnerii*, adjacent to § 11 *Si yconomus ecclesie prospexerit expedire...* . This note seems to give the personal name *Guarnerius* or French *Garnier*. Given the near-total absence of information on Garnier's person, this tiny note has to be examined. We would need to know how frequent a name Garnier was in those circles. In the « Getty Gratian » note, could it be the name of an *yconomus* i.e. a procurator, a cleric responsible for the finances and management of a church or religious house as the § 11 would indicate ? Could this same person be also Garnier the biographer, whose work, analysed in this paper, does indeed provide evidence for some interest in financial management (Thomas Becket's accountability after his election ; availability, in England, of charity-related social services in vacant religious houses ; availability of private financial support for the archbishop's prolonged stay on the continent)? A Garnier *yconomus*, responsible for the final accounting after the exile, would have had an easy inside access to all documents to be found at the site of the former exile court (even some copies of the archbishop's French letters ?). And, although no *Garnerius yconomus* is mentioned as a member of Thomas Becket's inner circle, a Garnier responsible for the finances of the house may have learned much about the archbishop's plans and actions. Indeed, Herbert of Bosham informs his reader :

« *cum... archipraesulem cum eruditibus suis hoc uel illud fecisse crebro audieris, ideo dictum noueris quia in agendis siue his quae ad Deum siue his quae ad saeculum, non admittebatur extraneus, praeterquam soli eruditi sui et consilarii forte alii, quales erant aeconomi* » (Robertson, Mat. 3, 139 ; 'when you will often be hearing

that the archbishop did this or that with his learned men, may you know that this is said, because, be their planned work God-related or world-related, no outsider was admitted, but only his learned men and maybe, as consultants, some others, like procurators’).

CONCLUSION

Thomas Becket’s letters *Expectans expectaui*, *Desiderio desideravi* and *Mirandum et uehementer stupendum*, all written in the year 1166 from his exile in France, are preserved in Latin in several collective manuscripts from the late 1170s on and also in French verse, in Garnier de Pont-Sainte-Maxence’s *Vie de Saint Thomas Becket* (finished ca. 1174). In his very solid edition (1922) of the French text, E. Walberg described Garnier’s work as a translation of the Latin letters. This paper questions Walberg’s theory.

It was found that the French letters included in Garnier’s verse (from ca. 1174) cannot be translations from any Latin letters of which the still-existing manuscripts would be direct copies, as the differences between the Latin and the French texts are too considerable. The French letters’ simple and clear style differs from the pompous, redundant and, at times, obscure expressions of the Latin letters. The French letters may give a text better suited for the situation and the recipient than the Latin text; and even a complete text where the Latin tradition has a lacuna.

Rather than as translations, this research would qualify the French letters preserved in Garnier’s verse as parallel texts to the Latin letters. This qualification is supported by the letter-writers’ diverging use of their common material. They may differ in their

interpretation of some expressions (« Christ's body » or « God's rod », *supra*) and their way of presenting and using quotations from the Bible or the *Decretum* is not the same. The Latin writer may give the quotations *uerbatim*, and leave it to the reader to apply them to the letter passage, while the French letters work those literary loans into the letter's message and make them easily understandable for the recipient. Of interest were the *Decretum* quotations : the Latin letter-writer quoting Gratian's Latin text and the French letter-writer using, in the corresponding passage, the same text according to the French *Decretum* translation, neither of them marking the canon law passage by its *incipit* or by the unit (*distinctio* ; *causa, quaestio*) in which it is found. This parallelism seems to show that the Latin and French letter-writers wrote their parallel texts in contact with each other.

If the French letters are accepted as original documents parallel to the Latin letters, but remaining outside the transmission of the Latin letters and untouched by their scribal (and editorial) alterations, they should not be disregarded as source material for Thomas Becket research.

While both the French and the Latin letters portray the exiled archbishop as a protector of God's Church against all attacks, may they come from the king himself, the impressions the French letters convey of Thomas Becket's relationship to the king and to Gilbert Foliot — the *de facto* leader of the English Church — differ considerably from those presented in the official Latin letters.

In the French letters, Thomas Becket wishes only the very best for the king, for whom he feels responsible and for whom he has sincere affection. Since he understands literally the biblical examples of

rebellious kings, whom God punished by destroying their wealth, but who, after repentance, got it back with God's blessing, he tries his utmost — prayers, admonitions, even threats of excommunication — to make the king respect what belongs to the Church and ultimately to God. — In the Latin letters he humiliates and offends the king.

In his French letter, Thomas Becket dislikes Gilbert Foliot whom he considers to be dishonest and cowardly. — In the Latin letter he is more conciliatory towards Gilbert Foliot.

In the French letters, Thomas Becket comes through as a vigorous, intelligent and honest person, whose language is clear and easy to read. — In the Latin letters, Thomas Becket is rather dull-witted and ridiculously keen on his own dignity.

The French letters are more coherent than the Latin ones. In his letters, while protecting the Church, Thomas Becket says repeatedly that he is the king's friend, that he has written to the king, that he wants to talk to the king ; he reprimands Gilbert Foliot for not taking care of the king. Only the French letters give an overall impression of affection and responsibility corresponding to Thomas Becket's description of his own feelings towards the king. – As (parts of) individual phrases, similar friendly thoughts and wishes can be found in the Latin letters as well, but they are in direct contradiction to the overall impression conveyed by these Latin texts. The official Latin letters correspond rather to the Thomas Becket image created by his opponents. Gilbert Foliot had called Thomas Becket stupid in public and, led by the Broc family, the crowd called Thomas Becket the king's traitor.

My theory of parallel texts could explain some of the differences of expression between the Latin and the French texts. Even when following the same guideline, two persons would write differently, especially if one of them (Thomas Becket ?) likes the recipient and is allowed to use his mother tongue, while the other (Herbert of Bosham ?) dislikes the recipient and has to adhere to Latin epistolary protocol.

The differences between the Latin and the French letters are so considerable, however, that I suspect that original letters, at least *Expectans* may have been 'edited'. For the French letters versified by Garnier, the possibility of secondary editorial alterations, be they corrections or falsifications, seems to be quite small, as the versified letters are an integral part of another text. Garnier's continental French dialect must also have discouraged any possible attempts to alter the text. Secondary 'editing' seems to be more likely for the Latin letters, no doubt accessible to the high clergy close to the king. Judging by Gilbert Foliot's letter, it was not in these people's interest that the friendship between Henry II and Thomas Becket be revived to allow Thomas Becket's return to his rightful position. Timewise, such 'editing' was possible, as there are several years between the earliest extant copies and the original letters written in 1166.

Finally, this paper suggests that Garnier, whose *Vie de Saint Thomas* seems to have saved, in French verse, an early version of Thomas Becket's letters, could have been a French-born procurator at the archbishop's exile court.

Tables

1. Comparison between some variants in the Latin Foliot manuscripts C (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS e Mus. 249) and D (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS Douce 287) and Garnier's French text for the letter *Expectans*. In the following, Duggan's edition text is followed, on the next line, by the variant(s) found in C and/or D (and in other Latin manuscripts used in the edition) and, thereafter, on a separate line, by Garnier's text.

(Duggan 328) l. 10 ... *quorum... consilio iam fere lapsus estis in profundum, quod absit, ne in profundum illud...*

(before *quod absit* add.) *sed u e r e o r* cCD

(compare to) ...*conseil.../ Qui te frea, ço c r i e m, si parfunt avaler/ Que ja mais ne purras resurdre* (Garnier 2858–2860) ;

(Duggan 330) l. 27 *nullatenus uidentur a potestate seculari posse uel debere percelli*

posse om. CD

Ne deit par poesté terriene perir (Garnier 2895, i.e. no equivalence for *posse*)

(Duggan 338) l. 2 *grauius est pondus sacerdotum*

var. *p o n t i f i c u m* CD

Li p r e l a t.../ Tant est greindre lur fais (Garnier 2994–2995) ;

(Duggan 338) l. 8 *consensit sanctum Iohannem Crisostonom ... expelli*

Iohannem om. ACV , interlin. B

*Saint Cristone suffri a essillier*⁸³(Garnier 3000, i.e. no equivalence for *Iohannes*);

(Duggan 340–342) the entire text l. 27 *Non uobis...* 342, l. 15 *penitebis*

⁸³ The saint is called *Seint Jehan Boche d'Or* in the *Decretum* translation D 96 c 10, l. 9.

om. CD

om. Garnier (3037).

(Duggan, all through the letter), the king is addressed using *uos*,

using *t u* CD

using *t u* Garnier

2. Comparison between some variants in the Latin manuscripts C (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS e Mus. 249) and D (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS Douce 287) and Garnier's French text for the letter *Desiderio*. As this letter is transmitted in a *grosso modo* identical fashion in Edward Grim's *Vita*, I give readings from this text (EG, in Robertson, Mat. 2: 419–421) as well. It will be seen that EG concurs with C and D in some, but not all of those instances where their Latin text mirrors Garnier's French text.

(Duggan 292) Heading *Thomas Cantuariensis archiepiscopus Henrico regi Anglorum*

No heading in EG (419)

Henrico regi Angl. Thom. Cant. Deo gratia minister humilis, s i n e s a l u t e m C

Ces lettres s e n z s a l u z enveia .../L'arcevesques al rei (Garnier 2041–3042)

(Duggan 292) l. 10 *Licet... Dei gratia cum habundantia uictualia ad sufficientiam habeamus*

cum abundantia... ad sufficientiam EG (420, like the edition text)

ad sufficientiam om DLV*

Deu merci, jo ai a mun vivre a plenté (Garnier 3058, i.e. no equivalence for *ad sufficientiam*)

(Duggan 294) l. 1 *debeo uobis et offero consilium meum et obsequium*

et obsequium om EG (420)

et obsequium om CV*

dei vus e voil vus conseillier (Garnier 3068, i.e. no equivalence for *et obsequium*)

(Duggan 294) l. 14 *ad malefactores ecclesie coercelandos*

var. *conterendos* EG (420)

var. *conterendos* CDLV*

Que les enemis Deu d e t r e n c h i e z (Garnier 3085, semantic similarity)

(Duggan 294) l. 21 *humiliauerunt se Domino*

humiliauerunt se Domino EG (420, like the edition text)

se Domino om C

Mult sunt humilié e furent en dolor (Garnier 3098, i.e. no equivalence for *Domino*)

(Duggan 296) l. 4 *Ecclesia enim Dei in duobus constat ordinibus*

ecclesia Dei EG (420, like the edition text)

Dei om C

En dous ordres de gent est faite saint' iglise (Garnier 3111, i.e. no equivalence for *Dei*);

(Duggan 296) l. 25 *nec cum scismaticis aliquam de cetero habeat communionem uel familiaritatem nec cum eis aliquo modo contrahat*

nec... contrahat om EG (421)

nec... contrahat om D

N'od les purvers n'aiez mais nul cumunement (Garnier 3150, i.e. no equivalence for *nec cum eis aliquo modo contrahat*)

(Duggan 298) l. 13 *possessionesque ad ipsam ecclesiam et nos pertinentes*

et nos om EG (421)

et nos om CD

E ses (i.e. those of Canterbury) *possessiuns e ses autres baillies* (Garnier 3171, i.e. no equivalence for *et nos*);

(Duggan 298) l. 17 *Permittatis etiam nobis, si placet... redire*

si placet om EG (421)

si placet om C

Laissiez nus repairier (Garnier 3176, i.e. no equivalence for si placet)

(Duggan 298) l. 18 *libere et in pace et cum omni securitate redire in sedem nostram, officioque... uti, sicut... ratio exigit*

officioque... exigit om EG (421)

officioque...exigit om CD

Laissiez nus repairier en pes e franchement (Garnier 3176, i.e. no equivalence for *officioque... exigit*).

Sometimes, EG's *Desiderio* text is closer to Garnier than any text used for the critical edition :

(Duggan 296) l.16 *trahere clericos ad secularia examina*

var. *j u d i c i a* (EG 421)

a voz j u i s e s ne a lei seculer (Garnier 3134).

(Duggan 298) l. 12 *temporibus predecessorum uestrorum et nostro rum* (two markers)

... *prædecessorum n o s t r o r u m* (EG 421 ; one marker)

... *as ancesurs e par antiquité* (Garnier 3170 ; no marker)

3. Comparison between some variants in the Latin manuscripts C (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS e Mus. 249) and D (Oxford, Bodl. Libr., MS Douce 287) and Garnier's French text for the letter *Mirandum*

(Duggan 434) l. 12 *Exigor itaque ab ea, que Ipse est, iusticia*

var *e o q u e e s t ipse iusticia C^{ac}*, and *e o q u i e s t ipsa iusticia D*

E D e u s, q u i e s t j u s t i s e, m e c o m a n d e e s u m u n t (Garnier 3460, i.e. the demanding subject is God and not the personification of Justice)

EG's *Mirandum* (Mat. 2, 409-412) text differs considerably from the *Mirandum* of the critical editions. The passage referring to a deal with Christ's body (in the middle of the letter in Duggan 432-434) marks the end of the letter proper in EG, followed only by the *salutatio* (from *Quos ... pretaxatarum* on). With its many and considerable lacunas, EG's *Mirandum* is shorter. Nevertheless, the beginning phrases and the ornate ending of the letter are practically the same in all Latin *Mirandum* texts, that of EG and those of the critical editions.

EG's *Mirandum* lacks all equivalence for much of the French letter text :

The following lines, all supported by the Latin *Mirandum* of the critical editions, have no counterpart in EG's *Mirandum*: 3333 (pulling a mountain down with a rope) ; 3343-3349 (*Est* and *non*) ; 3386-3390 (general praise and vague accusations) ; 3400 first half (*clauum teneo*) ; 3403-3422 (regarding Thomas Becket's alleged insignificance) ; 3442-3444 (regarding the entire kingdom's alleged opposition to Thomas Becket's promotion) ; 3451-3453 (Thomas Becket suspects continued opposition) ; 3456-3458 (and feels God's help) ; 3461-3462 (Thomas Becket opposing the recipient) ; 3481-3485 (quotation of arrows and innocent blood) ; 3492-3495 (God's will and secular court) ; 3503-3504 first half (quotation of the closest wall burning) ; 3521-3525 (the Jew's oath) ; 3528-3530 (two quotations) ; 3534-3545 (Constantine story) ; 3549-3555 (concern for Henry II and his reign). One notices that EG's *Mirandum* lacks several passages from Thomas Becket's polemic self-defense.

The reference to St Peter's cutting off the servant's ear, Garnier's lines 3488-3490, does not figure in EG's *Mirandum*; it is absent in the *Mirandum* of the critical editions of the Latin letters as well.

Edward Grim's *Mirandum* does not seem even meant to be a copy of an original. Avoiding many details, the author's truncated text serves well

his purpose: he tells about an exchange of letters between a group of English bishops under the leadership of Gilbert Foliot, and Thomas Becket, *ut... lector intelligat illos in exilio et desolatione sua sanctum archiepiscopum sensisse aduersarios a quibus debuit sperare solatium* (EG 409); and, after quoting the shortened *Mirandum* as an example of Thomas Becket's letters to them, he adds that the correspondence continued *ut hinc inde perpendatur, illi quidem quantæ devotionis ad justificandum opera regis, sanctus vero quantæ constantiæ in assertione veritatis exsisterit* (EG 412).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

TEXTS ANALYSED

La vie de S. Thomas le martyr par Guernes de Pont-Sainte-Maxence. Poème historique du XIIIe siècle (1172-1174), ed. Walberg, Emmanuel. 1922. Lund, Gleerup. (Skrifter utgivna av Kungl.hum. vetenskapssamfundet i Lund, 5.)

— *Guernes de Pont-Sainte-Maxence, La Vie de Saint Thomas Becket*. ed. Walberg, Emmanuel. 1936. Paris, Honoré Champion. (CFMA, 77.)

The Correspondence of Thomas Becket, Archbishop of Canterbury, 1162–1170, ed. and translated by Anne Duggan. 1–2. 2000. Oxford, Clarendon; New York, Oxford UP.

— In volume 1: *Desiderio desiderauit* (292–299); *Expectans expectaui* (328–343); *Que uestro pater* (372–383); and *Mirandum et uehementer stupendum* (426–441).

WORKS CITED

AND = Rothwell, et alii, eds. 1977-1992. *Anglo-Norman Dictionary*. London: Modern Humanities Research Association (www.anglo-norman.net).

Barlow, Frank. 1986. *Thomas Becket*. London, Weidenfeld and Nicholson.

Buridant, Claude. 2000. *Grammaire Nouvelle de l'ancien français*. Paris, Sedes.

Curtius, E.R. ed. 1911. *Li Quatre Livre des Reis*. Dresden - Halle, Niemeyer.

DEAF Bibl = *Dictionnaire étymologique de l'ancien français*. Möhren, Frankwalt, *Complément bibliographique* (www.deaf-page.de/bibl-neu.php).

Decretum, Latin text = Friedberg, Aemilius, ed. 1879. *Decretum magistri Gratiani*, editio Lipsiensis secunda. Leipzig: Tauchnitz. Photomech. Nachdruck 1959. Graz: Akad. Druck- und Verlagsanstalt.

—, Old French translation = Löfstedt, Leena, ed. 1992–2001. *Gratiani Decretum: la traduction en ancien français du Décret de Gratien I–V*. Commentationes Humanarum Litterarum, 95,99,105,110,119. Helsinki: Societas Scientiarum Fennica.

DMLBS = Latham, Ronald E., David Howlett, and Richard Ashdowne, eds. 1975

— 2013. *Dictionary of Medieval Latin from British Sources*. Oxford: British Academy.

Duggan, Anne. 1980. *Thomas Becket. A Textual History of His Letters*. Oxford, Clarendon.

— 2004. *Thomas Becket*. London, Arnold.

FEW = Wartburg, Walther von, et alii. 1922–2002. *Französisches etymologisches Wörterbuch*. Bonn, Leipzig & Basel: Zbinden.

Liebermann, Felix, ed. 1903–1916. *Die Gesetze der Angelsachsen* 1–3 (1 texts, 2 glossaries, 3 introductions and commentaries). Tübingen: Niemeyer. Repr. 1960 Sindelfingen: Scientia Aalen.

Löfstedt, Leena. 1990. « La loi canonique, les Plantagenêts et S. Thomas Becket » *Medioevo Romano*, 15: 3–16.

—1997. « La Vie de S.Thomas Becket par Garnier de Pont-Sainte-Maxence et la traduction en ancien français du Décret de Gratien ». *NM* 98 : 161-177.

—2010. « *Tu et vous*, un examen des formes verbales du singulier et du pluriel de la 2^e personne en ancien français ». *NM* 111/2010, 69-82.

—2015. « The MS. Ludwig XIV :2 (the « Getty Gratian ») and the Old French Decretum Translation ». *Romanica Cracoviensia* 2015/15 192–215.

Morawski, Joseph. 1925. *Proverbes français antérieurs au XIV^e siècle*. Paris, Champion.

Robertson, James Craigie and J.B. Sheppard, ed. *Materials for the History of Thomas Becket*. 1-7. 1875-1885. London, Longman. *Rerum Britannicarum Medii Aevi Scriptores* (here used: Vol. 1 (1875) for William of Canterbury's *Vita et passio S. Thomæ* (1–136); Vol. 2 (1876) for John of Salisbury's *Vita et Passio Sancti Thomæ* (301–322); and for Edward Grim's *Vita Sancti Thomæ*, (353–450, where EG's version of *Desiderio* 419-421; EG's version of *Mirandum* 409–412); Vol. 3 (1877) for William Fitzstephen's *Vita Sancti Thomæ* (1–147) and for Herbert of Bosham's *Vita Sancti Thomæ* (155–554); Vol. 5 (1881) for Robertson's critical editions of *Exspectans exspectaui* (269- 278); *Desiderio desideravi*, (278-282); and *Mirandum et uehementer stupendum* (512- 520).

Roques, Gilles, 2007. « Les régionalismes dans le Décret de Gratien ». *Mémoires de la Société Néophilologique de Helsinki* 70 : 217–230.

Schmidt, Paul Gerhard. 1989. « Thomas von Froidmont : Biograph des heiligen Thomas Becket. » *Sitzungsberichte der Wissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft an der Johann-Wolfgang-Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt am Main*, 25, 131–142. Stuttgart, Steiner Verlag.

— 1991. *Thomas von Froidmont : Die Vita des heiligen Thomas Becket [Vita et passio Sancti Thome]*. Stuttgart : Steiner Verlag.

Short, Ian, 2013. *A Life of Thomas Becket in Verse. Translated with an Introduction and Notes.* Toronto, Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies. (Mediaeval Sources in Translation, 56.)

Staunton, Michael, 2006. *Thomas Becket and His Biographers.* Woodbridge, Boydell.

T-L = Tobler, Alfred, Erhard Lommatsch, and Hans Helmut Christmann, 1925–2002.

Altfranzösisches Wörterbuch. 1–11. Berlin & Wiesbaden : Steiner.

Thomas, Jacques T.E.. 2002. *La Vie de Saint Thomas de Canterbury.* Louvain-Paris, Peeters.

Walberg, Emmanuel, 1915. *Affattningstiderna för och förhållandet emellan de äldsta lefnadsteckningarna öfver Thomas Becket.* Lund : Gleerup/Leipzig : Harrassowitz, Lunds Universitets Årsskrift N.F. I :10, nr 4.)